

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development

D1.2 – Report on project and SAB Meetings

WP1 – Manage & Coordinate

30/11/2023

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This report can be used for internally reviewing the project's progress and as a reference point for project partners on their tasks' completion regarding the agreed conditions by the consortium and as set out in the DIAMOND Grant Agreement.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

According to the project's Quality Management Plan, physical (in a hybrid format) and online meetings are organised regularly so that project partners can communicate and cooperate during the project's lifespan. Therefore, Executive Board (EB) meetings are hosted monthly as well as General Assembly (GA) meetings twice per year. The former are mainly hosted virtually, in one-hour sessions via Microsoft Teams, while the latter are either hosted online as two-day meetings or physically back-to-back with other physical events organised in the context of DIAMOND (as one- or two-day events), such as workshops. In-person GA meetings with no other back-to-back physical events are avoided for sustainability reasons. EB meetings are held to update all project partners on the progress of all Work Packages and to ensure that all deliverables and milestones are delivered on time as well as corrective actions—if necessary—are taken timely. In this context, the ICCS administration team hosts these monthly meetings and drafts their agenda, before finalising it with the entire consortium.

During the project's first year, two physical meetings took place: the Kick-Off Meeting in Athens, Greece on the 15th and 16th of December 2022, as well as the 1st General Assembly Meeting, in Bilbao, Spain on the 16th and 17th of May 2023. Moreover, 8 EB Meetings were organised via Microsoft Teams. Physical and online meetings alike feature high levels of attendance from the entire consortium, with all partners showcasing important dedication to the project's goals.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report is evidence of the accomplishment of DIAMOND's meetings as prescribed in the Grant Agreement. Additionally, the progress and completion of actions discussed in these meetings are and/or will be presented in the project's deliverables and milestone reports, which showcase the insightful research work accomplished in this project.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO SENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA' COOPERATIVA	IT	
SEURECO	SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
UM	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	NL	
ESMIA	ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC.	CA	
USMF	THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC	US	
UMD	UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND	US	
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	
ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	CH	
UNIBAS	UNIVERSITAT BASEL	CH	
Imperial	IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	UK	
Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
UCL	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UK	

Executive Summary

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1 Introduction

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, regular and ad hoc meetings are organised during the project's lifespan. General Assembly (GA) meetings are organised twice a year in order to oversee the progress of all actions realised as well as to aid partners in fully comprehending the scientific work conducted in the context of DIAMOND. The Project Coordinator (ICCS) is in charge of formulating the meetings' agenda, organising the meetings (in collaboration with Work Package leaders and all other partners), as well as informing all involved parties about the meetings' time and location; the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) members are also invited to attend these meetings. In addition, regular online meetings are organised (via Microsoft Teams), allowing partners to discuss specific issues regarding project deliverables, milestones, and tasks. Among these, monthly online Executive Board (EB) meetings are hosted by ICCS for partners to report, be informed on, and align with the project's actions and progress. ICCS record all meetings and sessions, in the context of various work packages and activities as well as the project's coordination and management. This report documents the latter (i.e., GA and EB Meetings), for which the project's administration team records meeting minutes and then shares them with the project's partners via the internal data management system (MS2), ensuring that the entire consortium is up to date with the project's timelines, agreed plans, and overall progress.

The following table depicts the meetings that took place during the project's first twelve months. EB meetings take place on a monthly basis, unless a GA meeting is held in the same month. Additionally, no EB meeting was organised in April 2023 and August 2023 due to limited availability related to Easter and summer vacations.

Table 1: DIAMOND Project Meetings (covering period December 2022-November 2023)

Type of meeting		Date
Physical	Kick-Off Meeting	15 th and 16 th of December 2022
Online	Executive Board Meeting	25 th of January 2023
Online	Executive Board Meeting	8 th of February 2023
Online	Executive Board Meeting	22 nd of March 2023
Physical	1 st General Assembly Meeting	16 th and 17 th of May 2023
Online	Executive Board Meeting	28 th of June 2023
Online	Executive Board Meeting	26 th of July 2023
Online	Executive Board Meeting	20 th of September 2023
Online	Executive Board Meeting	25 th of October 2023
Online	Executive Board Meeting	22 nd of November 2023

1.1 Purpose and scope

This deliverable aims to showcase a periodic report of all project meetings (physical and online), including the meetings' agenda, list of attendees, and meetings. Moreover, this deliverable includes any feedback provided by the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) from any online and physical communication, especially during dedicated SAB sessions typically held within GA meetings.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document comprises three sections. Section 2 is dedicated to presenting the agenda and minutes of physical meetings, Section 3 showcases all details from online meetings, and Section 4 presents the SAB's feedback.

2 Physical Meetings

2.1 Kick-Off Meeting, 15-16 December 2022

The project's Kick-Off Meeting was held on the 15th and 16th of December 2022 in Athens, Greece, where ICCS, the project's coordinator, is based. The main objective of this two-day meeting was for the consortium partners to discuss each other's expertise areas as well as their roles in the project and formulate a roadmap the DIAMOND's first twelve months. All partners (except UNIBAS, whose team members participated online) were represented physically by at least one of their team members.

2.1.1 Agenda

Day I: Full Project Overview

Virtual participants: Join us via Microsoft Teams ([link](#))

Thursday, December 15, 2022 (all times in CET)			
08:30 – 09:00	Arrival, coffee, get together		
09:00 – 09:10	I.1	Welcome, agenda, introductory notes	ICCS
09:10 – 10:20	I.2	Roundtable: Partners' Introduction Expertise, role, and expectations in DIAMOND (4' per partner)	All Partners
10:20 – 10:45	I.3	Project implementation for Horizon Europe Presentation and Q&A with Project Advisor	CINEA
10:45 – 11:00	Coffee Break		
11:00 – 11:15	I.4.1	Project Overview, Vision & Objectives	ICCS
11:15 – 11:30	I.4.2	WP1 – Manage & Coordinate Including coordination, management, quality processes	ICCS
11:30 – 11:50	I.4.3	WP2 – Codesign A mechanism for co-developing new model capacity and novel scenario exercises	ISINNOVA & ETH
11:50 – 12:10	I.4.4	WP3 – Update & Upgrade Improving the adequacy of Integrated Assessment Models	BC3
12:10 – 12:30	I.4.5	WP4 – Integrate & Expand Going beyond the structural limitations of Integrated Assessment Modelling	Imperial
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch Break		
13:30 – 13:50	I.5.1	WP5 – Apply & Explore Stretching the frontiers of the climate-economy modelling science	CICERO
13:50 – 14:10	I.5.2	WP6 – Open Establishing new business models for IAM transparency and legitimacy	ICCS & HOLISTIC
14:10 – 14:30	I.5.3	WP7 – Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit Academic, policy, and broader societal outreach, communication, dissemination, exploitation	HOLISTIC
14:30 – 15:00	I.6	Wrap-up, Q&A, Discussions	ICCS

For those joining Day I virtually, please use [Microsoft Teams](#).

Day II: Challenges, opportunities, near-term objectives

Virtual participants: Join us via Microsoft Teams ([link](#))

Friday, December 16, 2022 (all times in CET)			
08:30 – 09:00	Arrival, coffee, get together		
09:00 – 09:15	II.1	Synopsis of Day 1	ICCS
09:15 – 10:00	II.2.1	Challenges & Opportunities Each WP representative (5') presents two slides to address: - What are you most excited about in your WP & the project? - What are you most concerned about in your WP?	All partners
10:00 – 10:20	II.2.2	A quick summary of Year 1 deliverables & milestones	ICCS
10:20 – 10:45	II.2.3	Early project management requirements Scientific Advisory Board (SAB), Internal data management, Quality management, Meetings	ICCS
10:45 – 11:00	Coffee Break		
	II.3	Core model development (part A) State-of-the-art, Expansion & Development, Integration with other models	
11:00 – 11:25	II.3.1	GCAM-Europe	BC3, UMD, ICCS
11:25 – 11:50	II.3.2	OMNIA	E4SMA, Imperial, UCL, ESMIA
11:50 – 12:10	II.3.3	CLEWs-EU	Cyl, ICCS, Imperial
12:10 – 12:30	II.3.4	GEMINI-E3 EU	EPFL
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch Break		
	II.4	Core model development (part B) State-of-the-art, Expansion & Development, Integration with other models	
13:30 – 13:50	II.4.1	NEMESIS-World	SEURECO
13:50 – 14:10	II.4.2	OPEN-PROM	ICCS
14:10 – 14:50	II.5	Expanding model capabilities Expectations from model integration	All partners
14:50 – 15:00	II.5	Wrap-up, Q&A, Discussions	ICCS

For those joining Day II virtually, please use [Microsoft Teams](#).

2.1.2 Minutes

Present on Meeting	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Natasha Frilingou	ICCS
5	Themistoklis Koutsellis	ICCS
7	Panagiotis Fragkos	ICCS
8	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS
9	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
10	Jon Sampedro	BC3
13	Ignacio Cazcarro	BC3

14	Kurt Kratena	CESAR
15	Glen Peter	CICERO
16	Jan Ivar Korskbakken	CICERO
17	Ben Sanderson	CICERO
18	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
19	Alessandro Chiodi	E4SMA
20	Gabriele Cassetti	E4SMA
21	Alessia Elia	E4SMA
22	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
23	Georgia Polytanou	HOLISTIC
24	Andrés Ramos	Comillias
25	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
26	Carlo Sessa	ISINNOVA
27	Valentina Macclotti	ISINNOVA
28	Stefano Faberi	ISINNOVA
29	Pierre le Mouel	SEURECO
30	Paul Zagamé	SEURECO
31	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
32	Mark Sanders	UM
33	Sascha Serebriakova	UM
34	Prescott Morley	UM
35	Tania Treibich	UM
36	Eoghan O'Connell	UM
37	Friedemann Polzin	UM
38	Marie Pied	ESMIA
39	Doğancan, Beşikci	ESMIA
40	Marc Vielle	EPFL
41	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
42	Stephanie Briers	ETH
43	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
44	Ulf Hahnel	UNIBAS
45	Rui Mata	UNIBAS
46	Julius Fenn	UNIBAS
47	Lukas Engel	UNIBAS
48	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
49	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
50	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
51	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial
52	Mark Howells	Imperial
53	Alexandre Koberlë	Imperial
54	Michael Obersteiner	Oxford
55	Matthew Winning	UCL
56	Alvaro Calzadilla	UCL
57	James Price	UCL
58	Steve Pye	UCL
59	Olivier Dessens	UCL
60	Isabella Butnar	UCL

Minutes: Main issues discussed			
Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
Day I			
Introduction to the project and the partners	The meeting started with Prof Haris Doukas (ICCS) welcoming the partners and presenting the KOM's agenda. He also shared the mission of the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), as well as the academic and research activities of its research units, EPU-NTUA & E3MLab. He finally provided the projects' Work Packages (WP) and the role of ICCS. Dr Luis Olmos (Institute for Research in Technology - Comillas Pontifical University), Dr Dirk-Jan Van de Ven (Basque Centre for Climate Change), Dr Baptiste Boitier (SEURECO), Dr. Bianca Vienni Baptista (Transdisciplinarity Lab - ETH Zurich), Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial College London), Dr Gabriele Cassetti (E4SMA), Dr Constantinos Taliotis (Energy Planning and Analysis Group - Cyprus Institute), Dr Glen Peters (CICERO), Dr Marc Vielle (Laboratory of Environmental and Urban Economics - EPFL), Dr Ryna Cui (University of Maryland), Mr Doğançan Beşikçi (ESMIA), Prof Steve Pye (University College London), Prof Ulf Hahnel (University of Basel), Prof Mark Sanders (Maastricht University), Mr Carlo Sessa (ISINNOVA) took the floor to introduced their institute, team, and role in the project. Various other colleagues took the floor (physically or via Microsoft Teams) to introduce themselves.		
Project implementation for Horizon Europe	Ms. Silvia Vaghi, project manager in CINEA and DIAMOND's project officer greeted all partners, and started her presentation with a brief introduction on CINEA. Mrs Vaghi then moved on to key aspects related to the implementation of DIAMOND, highlighting two expected outcomes: the novel approach to go beyond the state-of-the-art by increasing the empirical relevance of economic models, including transdisciplinary aspects; and stakeholder engagement beyond the IAM community. She also stressed the compulsory nature of the Consortium Agreement (CA), and the Grant Agreement (GA) and went through some important articles of the GA, including Article 17 on Dissemination & Exploitation of the project and the importance of informing CINEA for any planned CDE activities and media events to help with the promotion of such actions and Article 21 on periodic reporting (M18, M36 and M48) with periodic & final reports to EC and payments requests, as well as continuous reporting through deliverables, milestones, etc. Apart from technical and financial aspects of the periodic reporting, she explained that the final review meeting is usually held one month before the end of the project. The reports should be submitted max. 60 days after the end of each reporting period, while payment should take up to 90 days after the submission of the report, given that the report is complete. Ms. Vaghi also presented DIAMOND's sister projects, namely PRISMA & WorldTrans, emphasising that many more projects present	Follow up with Ms. Vaghi regarding open-access rules in Horizon Europe projects	ICCS

	<p>opportunities for synergies (DECIPHER, PATTERN, etc). Prof. Doukas (ICCS) asked Ms. Vaghi a clarification regarding open-access publication and reimbursement from Horizon Europe projects, stressing that most high impact journals are hybrid, and this new rule would leave very few avenues for publishing, while Dr Nikas (ICCS) followed up with specific examples of high impact publications in Nature Climate Change from a previous project which recently ended, which would no longer be possible, and promised to get back to the project officer via e-mail with a formal question. Mrs Vaghi replied that indeed this rule is a novelty, and similar questions have been raised from other projects which have recently kicked-off; she promised to investigate further and come back to the project coordinator.</p>		
WP1 – Manage & Coordinate	<p>After the coffee break, Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) took the floor and provided an overview of the DIAMOND project, including its lifetime, the consortium, and its six objectives the methodology & structure of the project, briefly elaborating on the envisaged IAM enhancements, model interlinkages, and the numerous synergies of DIAMOND with other international modelling consortia, research communities, etc.</p> <p>He then delved into <i>WP1 - Manage & Coordinate</i>, with main goals the smooth project management and coordination, and contract administration with the EU, the implementation of a successful internal communication system (Microsoft 365 SharePoint) and quality management mechanism consisting of the quality control, and internal review processes (stressing the importance of respecting the provided timelines), and the fruitful communication with and steering from the project's transdisciplinary Scientific Advisory Board (SAB), including a presentation of the SAB synthesis.</p>	Set up the internal data management system	ICCS
WP2 – Codesign	<p>The meeting continued with Dr Vienni-Baptista (ETH) and Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) presenting <i>WP2 – Codesign</i>, which aims to apply a transdisciplinary approach to inform modelling improvements and ensuing scenarios.</p> <p>Dr Vienni-Baptista first discussed <i>Task 2.2: Phase 1 – Toward mutual understanding</i> and the joint discussion of the problem situation and research questions.</p> <p>She moved to <i>2.3.3 - Synthesis of co-produced knowledge</i> and described the situational analysis to explore the multiplicity of perspectives and nature of the transdisciplinary process.</p> <p>In the context of <i>Task 2.4: Phase 3 – Toward model co-ownership</i> the promotion of model co-ownership was stressed.</p> <p>Then, Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) discussed <i>Task 2.1: Developing an innovative stakeholder engagement plan</i>, and elaborated on the process to map relevant stakeholders and set up an engagement plan.</p> <p>On the remaining sub-tasks of T2.3, he mentioned that in <i>Task 2.3.1: Strategic foresight with stakeholders</i>, modellers, climate stakeholders and decision-makers will be invited to a programme of online events to co-define requirements for IAM improvement;</p>		

	<p>and on <i>Task 2.3.2: Values and practice driven foresight with citizens</i>, that groups of citizens will be invited to: define socially acceptable and preferable practices to simulate in the IAMs, evaluate whether reference scenarios fit with their perceptions, needs and desires, envision actionable practices and behavioural shifts towards more sustainable scenarios.</p> <p>The next steps to set up the stakeholder engagement plan were discussed.</p>		
<p>WP3 – Update & Upgrade</p>	<p>Dr van de Ven (BC3) together with Dr Gabriele Cassetti (E4SMA) took the floor to present <i>WP3 - Update & Upgrade</i>. They explained that the objective of this WP is to structurally improve six well-established IAMs, implement stakeholder-driven specifications (from WP2) in model development, where relevant, and harmonise assumptions for cross-model module integration (WP4) and inter-comparisons (WP5). Specifically, they mentioned that <i>Task 3.1 - Coordinated, stakeholder-driven development, harmonised data</i> will focus on the coordination of IAM core developments, while the remaining 6 tasks on the development and enhancement of each of the six models.</p>		
<p>WP4 – Integrate & Expand</p>	<p>Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) took the floor to present <i>WP4 - Integrate & Expand</i>. The objective of the WP is to develop modules to be integrated in the core IAMs that expand the capacities. She provided an overview of each task and the different dimensions these entail:</p> <p>Task 4.1 will focus on the soft link of ENGAGE CGE model to explore how increased circularity can help reduce emissions from energy-intensive industries.</p> <p>Task 4.2 will create scenarios of bioenergy production and land use emissions with the gridded land-use model MAgPIE</p> <p>Task 4.3 will expand household heterogeneity in the consumption modules of existing IAMs by adding the dimension of different household groups.</p> <p>Task 4.4 will represent the details of potential mitigation process uncertainties and their relationships to climate-carbon feedbacks using Open Simple Climate Models (SCM), allowing IAMs to solve for risk thresholds rather than likely temperatures.</p> <p>Task 4.5 will integrate stylized representations of financial and labour markets and heterogeneous consumers in IAMs. Regarding this task, Dr Ulf Hagnel noted that they also work on heterogeneity of consumer preferences and on agent-based modelling, and the potential synergies between tasks.</p> <p>Task 4.6 will develop a behavioral framework and identify the determinants of decisions and behavior change, perform data matching with household clusters (heterogeneity module (Task 4.3), and assess the mitigation potential of behavior change by integrating this module with IAMs;</p> <p>Task 4.7 will develop an interoperable interface of the openTEPES model and integrate it with technology-detailed IAMs model to assess future storage and network requirements.</p> <p>Finally, she presented the timeline of the relevant deliverables &</p>		

	<p>milestones under this WP.</p>		
<p>WP5 – Apply & Explore</p>	<p>Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) presented <i>WP5 - Apply & Explore</i>, with main objectives to employ the developed tools and explore a wide range of uncertainties and risks.</p> <p>He explained that in <i>Task 5.1</i> a systematic review of potential sources of bias in the scenario pipeline will be conducted, drawing on advances/insights from WP4. Also, in <i>Task 5.2</i> the potential for biases arising from missing coupling between human systems and climate impacts and unrepresented costs associated with climate adaptation in DIAMOND scenarios will be explored.</p> <p>In <i>Task 5.3</i> Imperial will undertake a structured assessment of “extremes” and disruptions, building from the stakeholder interaction exercises in Task 2.3.2 and augmenting these with expert interviews and surveys.</p> <p><i>Task 5.4</i> will focus on the implications of heterogeneous finance and on net-zero transition scenarios, outcomes on broader, multidimensional concepts of well-being, impacts of societal trends and behavioural changes, and distributional impacts of climate action as well as its interplay with circularity performance. Similarly, <i>Task 5.5</i> will take stock of all model improvements (WP3) and interlinkages with other frameworks (WP4) to broaden the IAM target space toward optimising overall sustainability performance of pathways to net zero.</p> <p>In <i>Task 5.6</i> CICERO will consolidate the findings of WP5 to produce a meta-analysis of risks associated with scenarios.</p> <p>Dr Shivika Mittal asked about potential synergies with PROVIDE and whether different SCMs could be used to feed scenarios into the IPCC, triggering discussions on climate sensitivity.</p>		
<p>WP6 – Open</p>	<p>Ms Natasha Frilingou (ICCS) & Dr Georgios Xexakis (XEXAKIS) presented <i>WP6 Open - new business models for IAM transparency/legitimacy</i>, with the main goals to continuously improve knowledge exchange (inside and outside the consortium), and ensure that research data and project outputs are FAIR (including through I²AM PARIS). In particular, <i>Task 6.1</i> will improve existing data explorers of I²AM PARIS, co-design new data explorers for specific audiences, create more result workspaces, and populate the platform with new datasets, modelling details, and software; <i>Task 6.2</i> will building communities of practice, and focus on capacity development; <i>Task 6.3</i> will create an open-source development pipeline; <i>Task 6.4: will ensure Credibility, and set up diagnostics, protocols, and stakeholder validation</i>; Finally, <i>Task 6.5: will update the I²AM PARIS platform</i>.</p> <p>These triggered discussions on the openness and transparency of models as well as improvements on the platform, with Dr Jon Sampedro (BC3) discussing the hosting of modelling documentation in GitHub will be connected to I²AM PARIS platform, Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) asked whether is feasible to document SDGs representation in each model and represent sectoral models, and Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) asked how can transparency could actually be enhanced, as scenario explorers and</p>		

	<p>documentation still remain a black box.</p> <p>Dr Xexakis replied that the advantage of the platform is that it provides a portal, without the need to replicate GitHub info but create other tools missing from GitHub (less technical, easier to navigate interface), and making the models more transparent and understandable. the platform can thus act as a mediator and also connector of several modelling communities, providing enough flexibility to accomodate such needs. Prof Doukas suggested that we should create a structured protocol with all the necessary inputs required to enhance transparency. Dr Mittal raised that transparency relates to the policy representation in each model and to model parameters and variables (like the discount rate), while Dr Peters suggested that we could focus on the most important aspects people are interested. Dr Vienni-Baptista noted that through WP2, we could better understand what stakeholders want to know, and help them understand how the models end up with specific results.</p> <p>Dr Nikas summarised the discussion concluding that by opening the models, we don't just mean provide an open-source code, but participating in communities of practice and promote collaboration and exchange.</p>		
WP7 – Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit	<p>Ms. Georgia Polytanou (HOLISTIC) presented <i>WP7- Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit</i> which will focus in the development and delivery of an impactful plan for CDE and a visual identity for the project, explain that <i>Task 7.1</i> will creating the DIAMOND visual identity and website, <i>Task 7.2</i> will develop an effective CDE plan and <i>Task 7.3</i> will focus on academic, policy, and overall societal outreach she mentioned that DIAMOND has already started a series of infographics connected to World Cup, showing per capita GHG emissions of the two countries in each match. Ms. Polytanou requested that partners submit visual identities and media channels for their institutions.</p> <p>Regarding academic publications, Dr Nikas (ICCS) commented on the new (game-changing) Horizon Europe guidelines for scientific publications, pending the response from the EC and requested that partners provide a list of journals that their institutions have agreements to cover the costs of the APCs</p>	<p>Creation of website and visual identity</p> <p>Create project templates</p> <p>Each organization's logo, short description, and website link; media channels used.</p> <p>Identify institutional agreements for APCs</p>	<p>HOLISTIC</p> <p>HOLISTIC</p> <p>All partners</p> <p>All partners</p>
Day II			
Challenges & Opportunities	Starting the day, each Work Package Leader took the floor and shared what are they most excited, as well as what are they most concerned about their WP & the project.		
A quick summary of Year 1 deliverables & milestones, and Early project	<p>Mr Koasidis (ICCS) presented an overview of key tasks starting during the first year of the project, associated with seven deliverables and five milestones (D3.1, D6.1, D7.1, D2.1, D1.1, D7.2, and D1.2).</p> <p>Dr Isabela Butnar (UCL) asked whether it is possible to share early</p>	Provide contact information to ICCS for mailing lists	All partners

management requirements	<p>on in the project which stakeholder groups are included and how each modelling group should interact with each stakeholder group. Mr Cassolà replied that they will distribute the list of stakeholders and the most pressing questions we receive from them as soon as these are available.</p> <p>Mr Koasidis then moved on to the early project management requirements, around MS1, MS2, D1.2 and D1.1, stressing the importance of a continuously updated internal mailing list.</p> <p>Dr Steve Pye (UCL) suggested to engage with NAVIGATE project.</p>		
Model Development Roundtable	<p>For each one of the core six IAMs, partners took the floor and presented the current state-of-the-art in their models planned developments, potential synergies with WP4 modules.</p> <p>Dr Jon Sampedro (BC3) presented how we move from GCAM to GCAM-Europe, Dr Casseti (E4SMA) presented the ambition of Open MuNdus Integrated Assessment (OMNIA) model to be a customised, open-access global IAM based on the TIMES framework, Dr Taliotis briefly presented Climate, Land, Energy and Water Systems (CLEWs), a Nexus modelling framework and the envisaged CLEWs-EU version, Dr Vielle (EPFL) presented GEMINI-E3 and the ambition to disaggregate main EU Member States, Dr Boitier (SEURECO) discussed the main ambition to provide NEMESIS-World the first open-source, global, large-scale, macro-sectoral model, and Dr Fragkos (ICCS) presented OPEN-PROM a the background of PROMETHEUS model, its regional and sectoral coverage, its focus on energy demand, as well as the model inputs and potential outputs. He then focused on OPEN-PROM and the spatiotemporal and technological updates from the core PROMETHEUS model.</p> <p>Within the discussions, colleagues raised numerous questions to which the presenters responding, regarding the way different aspects are modelled in each case, and the structure of the new models.</p>		
Wrap-up, Q&A, Discussions	<p>Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) suggested that a modelling survey should be created and completed by all modelling teams to enhance understanding among them; Dr Steve Pye (UCL) stressed that indeed small thematic workshops among modelling groups would really help enhance communication and exchange. Dr Sanders agreed that overlaps should be identified, data collection efforts combined, touchpoints to be established to operationalise communication, and he also proposed to host one such workshop in September 2023 at Maastricht. Dr Ulf Hahnel also commented that UNIBAS will catch up with the modelling teams during the workshops and address them by email, that they could join the OMNIA workshop planned in February if needed, and they could also organise a workshop on their behavioural module next year. Dr Sampedro also commented that each model would need to keep a degree of flexibility on how to integrate different aspects, as for example finance could be included through relatively simpler model tweaks but also though hard-coding new macroeconomic modules in the model.</p>		

Finally, Dr Nikas thanked the consortium for their time, and commented that ICCS will start communicating with everyone via a weekly update and regular emails in the next following days.		
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2.2 1st General Assembly Meeting: 16-17 May 2023

The 1st General Assembly Meeting was held in Bilbao, Spain, while after the GA the kick-off meeting of the GCAM-Europe model also took place. Team members who were not able to attend physically had the ability to participate through MS Teams. An SAB session also took place on the second day of the meeting (briefly presented here and in detail in Section 4), where SAB members were given the opportunity to provide feedback to the consortium regarding the project's objectives and progress.

2.2.1 Agenda

Day I

Virtual participants: Join us via Microsoft Teams ([link](#))

Tuesday, May 16, 2023, Barceló Bilbao Nervión (all times in CEST/local)			
10:00 – 10:30	Arrival, coffee, get together		
10:30 – 10:45	I.1	Welcome	BC3
task10:45 – 11:00	I.2	WP1 – Manage & Coordinate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination • Management • Quality processes (including review, review times, etc.) 	ICCS
11:00 – 11:45	I.3	WP2 – Codesign <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-layered Stakeholder Engagement Strategy • Planned stakeholder engagement activities • Synergies with and feeding information to WP3 & WP4 	ISINNOVA & ETH
11:45 – 12:00	Coffee Break		
12:00 – 13:00	I.4	WP3 – Update & Upgrade <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model Development Strategy • Models' kick-off meetings 	E4SMA & BC3
13:00 – 14:00	I.5	WP4 – Integrate & Expand <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress on module discussions • Climate module discussions (Task 4.4) 	Imperial & CICERO
14:00 – 15:00	Lunch Break		
15:00 – 15:30	I.6	WP5 – Apply & Explore <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early initiatives • Plan for kicking off WP5 in Year 2 	CICERO
15:30 – 16:15	I.7	WP6 – Open <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choosing Open Licenses • I²AM Paris Platform progress • OA publication strategy 	ICCS & Holistic
16:15 – 16:45	I.8	WP7 – Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual Identity • CDE plan 	Holistic

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website 	
16:45 – 17:00	I.9	Concluding Remarks	ICCS

Day II

Virtual participants: Join us via Microsoft Teams ([link](#))

Wednesday, May 17, 2023, Barceló Bilbao Nervión (all times in CEST/local)			
09:30 – 10:00	Arrival, coffee, get together		
10:00 – 10:15	II.1	Synopsis of Day I	ICCS
10:15 – 11:45	II.2	Focusing on the consumer-side <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Household Heterogeneity Consumer preferences and behaviours Well-being Labour and finance 	UNIBAS, CESAR & UM
11:45 – 12:00	Coffee break		
12:00 – 12:30	II.3	Circular Economy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The ENGAGE model 	UCL
12:30 – 13:00	II.4	Land use and agriculture <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The MAgPIE model 	Imperial
13:00 – 13:30	II.5	Electricity module <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The openTEPES model 	Comillas
13:30 – 14:30	Lunch break		
14:30 – 15:30	II.6	Scientific Advisory Board Introduction, project planning/implementation & feedback	SAB members, ICCS, all partners
15:30 – 16:45	II.7	Roundtable on WP3-WP4 collaboration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of modules to the core models Planned coverage expansions 	Imperial, all partners
16:45 – 17:00	II.8	Wrap-up, Q&A, Discussions	ICCS, BC3

2.2.2 Minutes

Present on Meeting	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Natasha Frilingou	ICCS
5	Themistoklis Koutsellis	ICCS
6	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
7	Panagiotis Fragkos	ICCS
8	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS
9	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3

10	Jon Sampedro	BC3
11	Claudia Rodes	BC3
12	Russell Horowitz	BC3
13	Ignacio Cazcarro	BC3
14	Kurt Kratena	CESAR
15	Glen Peter	CICERO
16	Jan Ivar Korskbakken	CICERO
17	Ben Sanderson	CICERO
18	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
19	Alessandro Chiodi	E4SMA
20	Gabriele Cassetti	E4SMA
21	Alessia Elia	E4SMA
22	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
23	Georgia Polytanou	HOLISTIC
24	Andrés Ramos	Comillias
25	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
26	Carlo Sessa	ISINNOVA
27	Valentina Maclotti	ISINNOVA
28	Stefano Faberi	ISINNOVA
29	Pierre le Mouel	SEURECO
30	Paul Zagamé	SEURECO
31	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
32	Mark Sanders	UM
33	Sascha Serebriakova	UM
34	Prescott Morley	UM
35	Tania Treibich	UM
36	Eoghan O'Connell	UM
37	Friedemann Polzin	UM
38	Marie Pied	ESMIA
39	Marc Vielle	EPFL
40	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
41	Stephanie Briers	ETH
42	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
43	Ulf Hahnel	UNIBAS
44	Rui Mata	UNIBAS
45	Julius Fenn	UNIBAS
46	Lukas Engel	UNIBAS
47	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
48	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
49	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
50	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial
51	Mark Howells	Imperial
52	Alexandre Koberlè	Imperial
53	Michael Obersteiner	Oxford
54	Matthew Winning	UCL
55	Alvaro Calzadilla	UCL
56	James Price	UCL
57	Steve Pye	UCL
58	Olivier Dessens	UCL

59	Isabella Butnar	UCL
60	Hannah Daly	SAB
61	Cecilie Mauritzen	SAB
62	David McCollum	SAB
63	Brian O' Gallachoir	SAB

Minutes: Main issues discussed			
Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
Day I			
WP1	<p>Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) greeted the partners and briefed them on the meeting's agenda. Next, Prof. Mikel González-Eguino (BC3) from the host partner institute welcomed all partners.</p> <p>Dr Nikas proceeded to the presentation on the progress of WP1, starting with Task 1.1 about the project's administration, reports and other processes (e.g., cost statements), as well as the bimonthly updates and the biannual calls between the project coordinator and the project advisor.</p> <p>He continued his presentation with Task 1.2 to confirm that all deliverables and milestones were submitted on time, and presented a list of deliverables and milestones that must be submitted in the project's 1st year. We also discussed the use of MS SharePoint.</p> <p>Dr Nikas mentioned that the internal review process in Task 1.3 has been effective so far since with only non-consequential delays that were well handled.</p> <p>He concluded his presentation with a brief summary of the current SAB synthesis which is expected to be finalised shortly.</p>	Finalise the synthesis of the SAB	ICCS
WP2	<p>Next, Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) took the floor and started the presentation of WP2. He commenced with an overview of the WP's objectives and then proceeded to a more thorough presentation of each Task.</p> <p>Mr Cassolà started with Task 2.1 regarding the stakeholder engagement plan and Deliverable 2.1, briefing the consortium on the knowledge integration process and the DIAMOND Participatory Foresight Space in which three groups of stakeholders will be involved: researchers, policymakers and citizens.</p> <p>Next, he proceeded to Task 2.3, explained to the partners how citizens will be involved as well as the stakeholder mapping process, and presented the timeline of the three workshops. In this context, Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) and Mr Cassolà discussed the importance of stakeholder mapping and engagement in the formation of the stakeholder database.</p> <p>Following this discussion, Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) presented the 1st phase of the codesign process, and the associated foresight workshops to produce stakeholder-informed research questions.</p> <p>Then, she proceeded to a schematic presentation of the Joint Problem Framing focusing on ETH's discussions with 4 IAM teams.</p> <p>Finally, Dr Briers mentioned that 2-3 online workshops will be</p>	<p>Prepare the stakeholder database and template for the mapping</p> <p>Preparations for the mutual understanding workshops</p>	<p>ISINNOVA, All partners</p> <p>ETH (to organise), all partners (to respond)</p>

	<p>organised between August and September to support mutual understanding between partners.</p> <p>Prof Sanders (UM), Dr Briers (ETH), Dr Vienni-Baptista (ETH), Dr Xexakis (HOLISTIC), Mr Koasidis (ICCS), and Dr Nikas (ICCS) discussed the purpose of the workshops, how these relate to other planned workshops, as well as the structure and length. Dr Briers stressed the importance of understanding the goals of each consortium partner and stated that stakeholder engagement will start to be reflected in the next deliverable. Mr Koasidis stressed the ensure that feedback from stakeholder engagement is on time to inform other project activities and Mr Cassolà followed up with a summary of an initial timeline.</p>		
<p>WP3</p>	<p>Next, Dr Jon Sampedro (BC3) took the floor, starting by presenting an overview of WP3 Tasks focusing on Deliverable 3.1 and the Model Development Strategy, the running survey monitoring the updates of the models and also requested that each modelling team keep the survey updated.</p> <p>Next, Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3) continued by presenting specifics on the 6 IAMs that will be upgraded by presenting the regions and sectors covered by the old and new versions and the interconnections of the 6 IAMs with the modules in WP4. In this context, Dr Constantinos Taliotis (CYI) mentioned that CLEWs-EU will also consider some data for non-EU countries such as the UK, Norway and Switzerland due to their proximity and interconnections with EU countries.</p> <p>Afterwards, Dr Gabriele Casseti (E4SMA) took the floor and briefed the consortium on the Kick-off meetings organised for the 6 project IAMs. The meetings for OMNIA and CLEWs have already taken place and the meeting for the GCAM EU model will take place the day after the General Assembly meeting, while the other three models (single-partner teams), there is no need for a similar meeting, but he requested that when decisions are made, the rest of the partners will be informed. Specifically, he proceeded to a short presentation of the OMNIA meeting and what was discussed.</p> <p>Dr Casseti also mentioned that the survey will be expanded to cover the Integration and Expansion strategy (link with WP4).</p> <p>Next, Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) suggested that it would be beneficial that a presentation for GEMINI-E3 EU and NEMESIS-World to take place since they are important components for WP4. Dr Nikas suggested that this could be done online.</p> <p>A discussion followed around the expansion of the survey to include aspects of WP4 with Prof Sanders (UM) and Dr Isabela Butnar (UCL) asking about the representation of specific policies as well as the timeline. Dr Casseti, Dr van de Ven and Dr Sampedro provided elaborations and explained that the survey is a living document continuously updated. In this context, Mr Koasidis, Dr Briers and Dr Casseti agreed that the consortium should communicate about the survey and how its results will be disseminated. Moreover, they agreed that the survey could be used for stakeholder engagement regarding WP2 and that the updated survey will be circulated for</p>	<p>Internally communicate the survey</p> <p>Update the survey</p>	<p>BC3, E4SMA</p> <p>BC3, E4SMA, All modelling WP3 and WP4 teams</p>

	stakeholder and partner workshops as well.		
WP4	<p>Next, Prof Adam Hawkes (Imperial) took the floor and proceeded with an overview of WP4 and the progress that has been achieved so far and he mentioned that although no deliverable is already submitted, a lot of work has already been done (e.g., workshops).</p> <p>Next, Prof Kurt Kratena (CESAR) made a short presentation for Task 4.3 focusing on the 3 dimensions of household heterogeneity (i.e., income, socio-economic status as well as attitudes and values). Also, he mentioned that the next step is the improvement of the consumption modules in GEMINI-E3 EU and NEMESIS-World.</p> <p>Prof Sanders (UM) briefed the partners on Task 4.5, which focuses on finance, labour, consumer behaviour and energy transition and reiterated UM's intention to host a meeting in autumn, Prof Rui Mata (UNIBAS) presented an overview of the goals of Task 4.6, focusing on the Behavioural Module Development, Dr Ben Sanderson (CICERO) presented Task 4.4 and the linkage between IAMs and climate/physical impact models. Dr Sanderdon also mentioned that Task 4.4 strategy will be to build an interface connecting project IAMs with the existing Open SCM infrastructure, aiming for a rapid assessment of regional, probabilistic climate data from IAM simulations with the METEOR framework. Lastly, Dr Mittal and Dr Sanderson had a short discussion on regional integration with IAMs, the capacity of different METEOR versions (a new one will be developed) and the inclusion of geoengineering.</p>	Communicate about the workshop on finance, labour and consumption	UM
WP5	<p>Afterwards, Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) proceeded with the presentation of WP5's timeline and an overview of the tasks that are scheduled to start beyond the first year of the project. He also demonstrated a schematic illustration of scenario pipeline uncertainties (related to Task 5.1) showing emissions uncertainties and results from different climate models. Next, Dr Mittal, Dr Peters and Dr Sanderson discussed the sensitivity analysis and correlations regarding climate results. Lastly, Prof Tania Treibich (UM) and Dr Peters discussed the effect of labour parameters and policies on climate models and Dr Mittal also mentioned the issue of climate scenarios affecting capital costs etc.</p>		
WP6	<p>Next, an overview of the progress so far and the future planning of WP6 was presented by Mr Koasidis (ICCS) and Dr Xexakis (HOLISTIC). They informed the partners on the submission of Deliverable 6.1 and briefed the consortium on the machine-actionable Data Management Plan (DMP) stored in Argos, as well as the preparation of Milestone 4.</p> <p>Mr Koasidis presented the options on possible licenses that each model could adopt, and decisions made, mentioning that there is no decision yet regarding GEMINI-E3 EU to first understand the conflict regarding the GTAP database. Dr Sampedro suggested that the data can be separated from the model, but Dr Vielle (EPFL) replied that this is not so easy for GEMINI-E3. Both Mr Koasidis and Dr Xexakis suggested that we should strive to make everything as open as possible.</p> <p>Next, the use of the project repository on GitHub was disuccsed,</p>		

	<p>with Dr Mittal suggesting that a joint meeting must take place to further discuss this issue.</p> <p>Then Mr Koasidis presented the strategy to publish scientific publications with open access per EC guidelines, and Dr Xexakis elaborated on the material required to be uploaded onto Zenodo.</p> <p>Afterwards, Dr Xexakis and Mr Koasidis informed the partners about the I²AM PARIS platform and new features to be added such as validation routines, as well as communities of practice.</p> <p>Following this, a discussion took place between Dr Xexakis, Dr Vienni-Baptista, Mr Koasidis and Dr Briers related to ethical issues regarding data collection and ETH's protocol around such aspects.</p> <p>Lastly, Dr Xexakis presented the IP scan service focusing on what it does, and the main challenges associated with it and Dr Cassetti intervened making 5 main recommendations.</p>		
WP7	<p>To close the first day of the meeting, Ms Georgia Polytanou (HOLISTIC) briefed the partners on the WP7 objectives and activities, mentioning that the CDE plan and website of the project are already created and presented the visual identity of the project and the progress so far as well as the next steps (e.g., infographics and videos) and demonstrated the website's structure. In addition, she demonstrated an overview of the CDE's contents and a summary of the project's current synergies. Lastly, she briefly presented the planning of the WP so far, with D7.1 being submitted and D7.2 being under review.</p>		
Day II			
Focusing on the consumer-side	<p>After Dr Nikas greeted the partners and briefed them on the discussions of Day 1, he informed the partners that Day II discussions will focus on the WP4 modules and be coordinated by Dr Mittal.</p> <p>The 1st session, focusing on consumer-side issues, was opened by Prof Ulf Hahnel (UNIBAS), who briefed the partners on the two online workshops that took place in January and March of 2023 and helped identify main research questions and presented a summary of a proposed timeline for the next months on this synergistic approach.</p> <p>Then, Prof Hahnel (UNIBAS) presented issues related to behavioural aspects and notably integration opportunities referring to two extreme scenarios regarding public support.</p> <p>Afterwards, Dr Kratena took the floor and mentioned challenges related to consumer-side issues, briefly presented modelling work done considering heterogeneity using the WILIAM model for the LOCOMOTION project, and he focused on ways that behavioural change and heterogeneity can be combined. In this context, Dr van de Ven, Dr Sampedro and Prof Kratena discussed heterogeneity data for models, with Prof Kratena mentioning that transport data for the EU are easily available, whereas household data are more difficult to find and sometimes they have to be matched. In response, Prof Hahnel said that income can be easily accessed through surveys, and he also asked how the household clusters were chosen in the LOCOMOTION project with Prof Kratena replying that the household size was the main factor. In a similar context, Dr Mittal and Prof</p>		

	<p>Kratena discussed the distribution of mitigation policies in households. Lastly, Dr Nikas and Dr Sampedro had a discussion on how each modelling team can incorporate these issues and Prof Kratena suggested that this can be determined after the Model Development Strategy is prepared.</p> <p>Next, Mr Prescott Morley (UM) took the floor and presented how well-being affects behavioural changes linking with the work that will be done with UNIBAS and CESAR. Then, Mr Morley added that it is difficult to get final demand equations from IAMs, which could be proven very useful. Dr Vielle mentioned that relevant feedback could be provided from the updated survey. In this context, Dr Casseti asked if the social context of these studies focuses on Western cultures with Mr Morley replying that studies have focused on the EU and the USA, but many mechanisms are quite universal (they have spotted minor differences in China).</p> <p>Mr Eoghan O’Connell (UM) and Ms Sascha Serebriakova (UM) finally discussed topics on labour and finance aspects and the respected modules to be developed. In this context, Dr Nikas had two questions: a) labour and finance are interconnected, will they be modelled separately? and b) how can these improvements be incorporated in IAMs apart from CGE models? Prof Sanders stated that labour and finance have many common points; hence the modules will be independent, but connections will exist in order to work stand-alone but to be able to be integrated as well. He also mentioned that integrating these modules in IAMs requires important cooperation with modelling teams</p>		
<p>Circular Economy</p>	<p>Next, Mr Matthew Winning (UCL) took the floor and introduced the concept of circular economy and a summary of the ENGAGE model, the current state-of-the-art, and two existing applications of the model in research. Including one linking the ENGAGE model with TIAM-UCL. To conclude his presentation, Mr Winning briefed the partners on the current and future extensions of the ENGAGE model. Afterwards, Dr van de Ven and Mr Winning discussed the presented applications and Dr Mittal and Mr Winning had a conversation about policies that can be included regarding steel production.</p>		
<p>Land use and agriculture</p>	<p>In the next session, Dr Alexandre Koberlè (Imperial) focused on the MAgPIE land-use model, how the model functions, as well as focuses on the regional coverage. He mentioned that some limitations of MAgPIE are the unavailability of raw datasets and the fact that the code is not open but if the datasets and code can be somehow aggregated, the model can be open-source. Next, he presented some model outputs (derived from an online tool) and proceeded to an overview of the Postdam IAM framework, which combines the REMIND and MAgPIE models. He suggested that the same framework can be used by replacing REMIND with OMNIA and OPEN-PROM. To conclude his presentation, Dr Koberlè demonstrated some research applications. Lastly, Dr Anastasis Giannousakis (ICCS) and Dr Koberlè discussed the coupling of OMNIA and MAgPIE, focusing on the relevant documentation. They mentioned that a soft linkage is feasible, exchanging key variables.</p>		

	In this discussion, the importance to identify how to model agriculture was also raised, indicating that there are possible data issues.		
Electricity Module	Next, Prof Andrés Ramos (Comillas), introduced the consortium to the openTEPES fully open-source power sector model. He presented the main development goals of the openTEPES team, some of which are to make the model simple and provide a flexible duration of the time step, as well as projects that the model has been used. Moreover, he demonstrated the main modelling features of openTEPES mentioning that energy storage is at the core of the model. He explained that the model has been linked with TIAM-ECN GUSTO, EMPS-W, openENTRANCE and TIMES-SINERGIA. In this context, Dr van de Ven and Prof Ramos discussed the integration with GCAM and Dr Mittal and Prof Ramos discussed the combination of TIAM-ECN and openTEPES at the European level.		
SAB session	Dr Nikas took the floor and, after greeting the SAB members, made a short introduction to the project, its duration, partners, objectives, methodology, structure, and the Horizon Europe ecosystem of projects examining similar scientific fields. He briefed SAB members on the project's focus on stakeholder engagement and open science alongside envisaged model development, and he discussed how the consortium envisions interacting with them. Afterwards, the 4 present SAB members (Dr Cecilie Mauritzen from MET Norway, Prof Hannah Daly and Prof Brian O' Gallachoir from University College Cork, and Dr David McCollum from Oak Ridge National Laboratory) introduced themselves with Dr Nikas mentioning that their expertise is crucial, and that the consortium looks forward to receiving the SAB's feedback on the work done in the project. Next, Dr Mauritzen and Dr Nikas discussed the importance of stakeholder engagement and ways to achieve that. Dr McCollum added that he is thrilled to advise the consortium on issues that may come up and the consortium may be unaware of. Then, Dr Nikas, Dr Mittal, Dr McCollum, and Prof O' Gallachoir had a short discussion on events and conferences that can be insightful for the project's progress. Next, Dr Mauritzen made a short presentation on the WorldTrans sister project, coordinated by MET Norway, which belongs to said Horizon Europe project ecosystem. Finally, Dr Nikas thanked the SAB members for their presence and stated that their notes were very insightful.		
Roundtable on WP3-WP4 collaboration	After the SAB session ended, Dr Mittal informed the partners that the consortium intends to collect info from modelling teams on the interactions of WP3 & WP4. In this context, Dr Cassetti mentioned that modellers have already been asked to update the relevant survey but due to communication issues, there are still some pending issues. The main objective of the survey is to examine which IAMs can be linked with which sectoral modules and how, focusing on the linking methodology and its requirements. Next, Dr Pierre Le Mouël (SEURECO) mentioned that the NEMESIS-World model can be linked with ENGAGE as well as the climate modules developed by CICERO. In the same context, Dr Cassetti informed the consortium that the		

OMNIA model can be linked with openTEPES, ENGAGE and MAGPIE as well as the behavioural change (UNIBAS), heterogeneity (CESAR) and climate (CICERO) modules. Then, Dr Mittal, Dr Giannousakis and Dr Koberlè had a short discussion on linking MAGPIE with OMNIA. Moreover, Dr Mittal suggested that the partners should start a more thorough work defining parameters and Dr Sampedro replied that the presented survey acts as an initial form. Next, Dr van de Ven and Dr Sampedro stated that the GCAM model can be linked with every module from WP4 except the heterogeneity module. Similarly, Dr Vielle stated that the GEMINI-E3 EU model can be linked to the finance (UM), heterogeneity and climate modules as well as the openTEPES model. Afterwards, Dr Giannousakis informed the partners that the OPENPROM model can be linked with every module except the finance/labour and behavioural change modules. Next, Dr Taliotis took the floor and mentioned that CLEWs-EU can be linked with climate, finance/labour and behavioural change modules focusing on issues such as crop yields, capital for investment and modal shift respectively.

After all modelling teams presented the potential linkages with WP4 modules, Dr Mittal and Mr Winning discussed how to share data between modelling teams, especially regarding the sectoral modules and they suggested that a survey may be required. In this context, Dr Briers and Dr Vienni-Baptista proposed that it would be interesting to find/examine interlinkages from the joint problem-framing process. Next, Mr Koasidis asked if there is any need for further input from the partners regarding WP4 and Dr Sampedro added that the consortium has to finalise the work in the potential interconnections, and he suggested that a bilateral exchange with partners can take place. In this context, Dr Mittal suggested that bilateral meetings can take place (between modelling teams from WP3 & WP4) to determine the scope of the linkages, with Mr Winning supporting this idea. Then, Mr Koasidis mentioned that the Model Development Strategy will need take into consideration stakeholder feedback. Moreover, Dr Briers and Dr Nikas has a short discussion on how to incorporate these issues into the GCAM workshop, that will take place the next day. In this context, Dr Mittal said that this discussion is a good starting point for further discussions with WP3 leaders. Lastly, to conclude this session, as well as, the whole GA meeting, Dr Nikas proposed to have follow-up meetings for such issues and thanked the BC3 partners for hosting this event as well as all partners that participated online.

3 Remote (Online) Meetings

3.1 Executive Board Meeting – 25 January 2023

3.1.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 25 January 2023
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - MS1: Formulation of the SAB (ICCS) – January 2023
 - Mailing lists (ICCS)
 - MS2: Internal data management (ICCS) – March 2023
 - Quality management (ICCS)
 - WP2: Codesing
 - Engagement strategy (ETH & ISINNOVA)
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - D3.1: Model development strategy (BC3) – March 2023
 - CLEWs kickoff meeting (Wed 18/01)
 - OMNIA kickoff meeting (03/03)
 - GCAM kickoff meeting (TBD)
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Household representation meeting (UM, CESAR, UNIBAS)
 - Next meetings? (Imperial)
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - WP6: Open
 - Open data management plan (ICCS, HOLISTIC) – March 2023
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - D7.1: Visual Identity & website (HOLISTIC) – March 2023
 - Document templates (ICCS & HOLISTIC)
 - Open access publication strategy (ICCS)
2. Pending requests – ICCS & All Partners
3. Project social media & partner introduction posts – HOLISTIC & all partners
4. Any other business

3.1.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Natasha Frilingou	ICCS
5	Haris Doukas	ICCS
6	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS
7	Jon Sampedro	BC3
8	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
9	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
10	Glen Peters	CICERO
11	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
12	Gabriele Cassetti	E4SMA
13	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
14	Georgia Polutanou	HOLISTIC
15	Luis Olmos Camacho	COMILLAS
16	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
17	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
18	Kathleen Vailancourt	ESMIA
19	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
20	Marc Vielle	EPFL
21	Rui Mata	UNIBAS
22	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
23	Stephanie Briers	ETH
24	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
25	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
26	Vingesh Sridharan	Imperial
27	Steve Pye	UCL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) started the meeting by greeting the partners and proceeded to inform the partners that on the 24 th of January the Milestone report for the tentative synthesis of the SAB was submitted to the EC (MS1), while MS2 (Internal Data Management System and D1.1 (quality management plan) based on what was presented in the KoM are well underway. In this context, Dr Nikas informed that the NDA does not change before communicating with the SAB candidate members. Dr Nikas also requested that partners make sure that everyone is included in the relevant mailing lists.	Get in touch with SAB candidate members	ICCS
		Complete the deliverable for MS2	ICCS
		Prepare D1.1	ICCS
		Update mailing lists	All partners
WP2	The discussion on WP2 commenced by Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) who informed the consortium that his team is	Provide ISINNOVA with	All partners

	<p>already working on the development of the stakeholder engagement plan and he requested that partners provide him suggestions for stakeholders to be included in our database.</p> <p>Afterwards, Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) mentioned that she is meeting with all modelling teams to understand what each model exactly does, so we can better coordinate stakeholder engagement efforts. Moreover, Dr Briers discussed the first WP2 coordination meeting between the ETH and ISINNOVA partners, taking place on the 26th of January. In this context, Dr Nikas suggested that ICCS also participates.</p>	<p>potential stakeholders</p> <p>ETH to host a coordination call for WP2</p>	<p>ETH, ISINNOVA, ICCS</p>
WP3	<p>Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3) and Dr Gabriele Cassetti (E4SMA) informed the partners about work under D3.1 and the aspiration to roll-out a survey for WP3 modelling teams to map envisaged model developments. A template for the survey will be delivered in the next few days and that E4SMA will start collecting information on models' input and output. Modelling meetings will be facilitated by this data.</p> <p>Prof Haris Doukas (ICCS) intervened stressing the need to potentially perform a similar survey with the co-design process, to which, Dr Bianca Vienni-Baptista (ETH) said that this survey can also be linked to Task 2.2. aiming to identify aspects that should be discussed and then included in the models. Dr van de Ven agreed with both speakers.</p> <p>Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) asked about the structure of the survey, with Dr Cassetti replying that details are not yet defined but will be shared with the consortium.</p> <p>Lastly, Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) and Dr Xexakis discussed the focus of the survey (modelling capabilities) and the template that should be used for WP3 & WP4.</p> <p>The kick-off meetings of individual models was also discussed. Dr van de Ven suggested a joint meeting with EPFL and SEURECO teams, which use the GEMINI-E3 and NEMESIS models respectively. Dr Marc Vielle (EPFL) and Dr Baptiste Boitier (SEURECO) agreed that is a potential option. The timeline for the meetings on GCAM-Europe and OPENProm was also discussed, along with the possibility of a GCAM training session in Bilbao. Dr Nikas suggested that GCAM, OMNIA and CLEWs models must be prioritised since more partners are involved in their expansion, while Prof Doukas stressed that WP2 could be included in these modelling meeting.</p>	<p>Finalise template and roll out model survey</p> <p>Organise modelling Kick-off meetings</p>	<p>E4SMA, All modelling partners</p> <p>All modelling partners</p>
WP4	<p>Following the discussion on WP3, which included aspects related to WP4, Prof Adam Hawkes (Imperial) added that there can be a survey on the stakeholders' perspective on model linkages to follow up on the survey of WP3, and that discussions on meeting for WP4 can be held the following period. Dr Nikas stressed that WP4 requires great collaboration involving the right people.</p>		

WP5	Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) informed the partners that WP5 formally starts in M13 (December 2023) and that the survey already discussed can a useful internal communication tool. He also said that preparatory processes could start in the second semester of 2023.		
WP6	Dr Nikas informed on the development of a machine-actionable data management plan. Dr Xexakis mentioned that the ARGOS tool (provided by OpenAIRE) will be used and he described the functions of machine-actionable datasets. He also stressed the novelty of this process compared to conventional DMPs, which may require a more active role by all partners. In this line, along with the DPM Dr Nikas stressed the importance of opening up the project's results.	Prepare the data management plan	ICCS, HOLISTIC
WP7	Ms Georgia Polutanou (HOLISTIC) took the floor and informed the partners that there will be no modifications to the project's logo since no objections were made during the Kick-off meeting. Ms Polutanou also informed the partners about the project's social media accounts which are active. Moreover, Ms Polutanou informed the consortium that the project's deliverables template is ready. Lastly, Dr Nikas requested that all partners respond to ICCS's call for information on publishing journals with institutional agreements. In this context, Dr Mittal informed the consortium that Imperial has a long database.	Finalise visual identity of project Inform partners about social media accounts Provide list of journals with institutional agreements	HOLISTIC HOLISTIC All partners

3.2 Executive Board Meeting – 08 February 2023

3.2.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 08 February 2023
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Mailing lists (ICCS)
 - MS2: Internal data management (ICCS) – March 2023
 - WP2: Codesing
 - WP2 kickoff meeting (26/01)
 - Engagement strategy (ETH & ISINNOVA, all partners)
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - D3.1: Model development strategy (BC3) – March 2023
 - Survey to collect the inputs and outputs from (E4SMA)
 - CLEWs physical meeting (24/04)
 - OMNIA physical meeting (03/03)
 - GCAM physical meeting (TBD)
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Follow-up meeting on the consumer side (UM, CESAR, UNIBAS) and engagement with modelling teams (Feb-Mar, TBD)
 - Next meetings? (Imperial)
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - WP6: Open
 - Open data management plan (ICCS, HOLISTIC) – March 2023
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - D7.1: Visual Identity & website (HOLISTIC) – March 2023
 - Document templates (ICCS & HOLISTIC)
 - Follow-up on open access publication strategy (ICCS)
2. Pending requests – ICCS & All Partners
3. Project SMEs and European Commission's IP Scan (E4SMA)
4. Any other business

3.2.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation

1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Natasha Frilingou	ICCS
5	Haris Doukas	ICCS
6	Themistoklis Koutsellis	ICCS
7	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS
8	Jon Sampedro	BC3
9	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
10	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
11	Glen Peters	CICERO
12	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
13	Gabriele Casseti	E4SMA
14	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
15	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
16	Sara Lumbreras Sancho	COMILLAS
17	Luis Olmos Camacho	COMILLAS
18	Andrés Ramos Galán	COMILLAS
19	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
20	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
21	Paul Zagamé	SEURECO
22	Doğancan Beşikci	ESMIA
23	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
24	Marc Vielle	EPFL
25	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
26	Stephanie Briers	ETH
27	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
28	James Price	UCL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	<p>The meeting started with Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) greeting the partners and informing them that regarding the SAB synthesis, many stakeholders have already shown their interest. Lastly, Dr Nikas informed the consortium that the mailing lists for each WP, etc are close to being finalised.</p> <p>Dr Nikas discussed the organisation of the General Assembly Meeting, with some partners volunteering to host it. Dr Nikas also suggested that it could be beneficial to invite SAB members and inform them on the project.</p>	<p>Include all the appropriate researchers and personnel in the mailing lists</p> <p>Initiate discussions on the next GA</p>	<p>All partners</p> <p>ICCS</p>
WP2	<p>Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) briefed the consortium regarding the progress on WP2 in light of the WP's kickoff meeting that took place on the 26th of January.</p> <p>Afterwards, Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) informed the partners about Task 2.2 and the planning phase for modelling teams' engagement. In this context, she requested from modelling teams to discuss policy questions during their internal</p>		

	<p>meetings.</p> <p>Afterwards, Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) informed the partners about Task 2.2, which focuses on the planning phase for modelling teams' engagement. In this context, she requested modelling teams to discuss policy questions during their internal meeting.</p> <p>Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) asked how should WP3 include WP2. Mr Cassolà said that WP3 should take into consideration the mapping of the stakeholder needs and that the policy questions must be in line with WP3.</p>		
WP3	<p>Dr Jon Sampedro (BC3) mentioned that the internal meetings each modelling team will have the flexibility to determine how the work on WP3 will proceed. Regarding the survey, Dr Gabriele Cassetti (E4SMA) informed the partners that collection of information is underway and that the finalised version will be available next week. He also mentioned that information must be shared with partners on how to connect models for WP4.</p> <p>Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) proposed that HOLISTIC can help with the survey regarding WP6 aspects and Dr Cassetti replied that he will share it with HOLISTIC as soon as the structure is finalised. In this discussion, Dr Marc Vielle (EPFL) asked a question on the harmonisation of data collection and Dr Sigit Perdana (EPFL) replied that this can be discussed after the completion of the survey.</p> <p>Afterwards, the discussion moved to the modelling teams' internal meeting and the scheduling of the CLEWs-EU and OMNIA meetings. Dr Nikas informed the partners that there are still discussions with BC3 regarding the GCAM meeting, which will probably take place in September. Lastly, Dr Briers asked that the ETH team participates in single-team modelling meetings since it can be useful for stakeholder engagement.</p>	<p>Finalise the survey</p> <p>Organise the CLEWs-EU meeting</p> <p>Organise the OMNIA meeting</p> <p>Organise the GCAM meeting</p>	<p>E4SMA, modelling teams</p> <p>ICCS, Imperial, Cyl</p> <p>E4SMA, Imperial, UCL, ESMIA</p> <p>BC3, ICCS, UMD</p>
WP4	<p>Proceeding to WP4, Dr Mittal said that we should start with the survey template which will contribute to the harmonisation between sectoral models. In this context, there is a necessity to understand the information collected from the survey on IAMs and sectoral models. Furthermore, Dr Mittal suggested that the joint meeting of WP3 and WP4 could take place after the internal meetings, around May or June. In this context, Dr Nikas mentioned that there are no official meetings for single-team models and that the consortium should not wait until all internal meetings are completed since the GCAM meeting will take place in September.</p>	<p>Organise the joint meeting between WP3 & WP4</p>	<p>Imperial</p>
WP5	<p>Afterwards, Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) informed the partners that there is not much progress since the WP starts later on. Nevertheless, the harmonisation discussion is very important for WP5 as well, and explained possibilities for synergies with projects on this matter. In this discussion, Dr Cassetti</p>	<p>Prepare a survey for WP5</p>	<p>CICERO</p>

	<p>proposed that aspects from WP5 should be included in the initial survey, which will collect data until the beginning of March. Moreover, Dr Mittal proposed that a harmonisation database is created in Microsoft Teams. Lastly, Dr Peters stressed the challenging issues regarding land modelling and in this context, Dr Mittal proposed that WPs 3, 4 and 5 should be coordinated to answer all the relevant questions.</p>		
WP6	<p>Next, Dr Xexakis informed the partners that the updates on the platform are still under development. Furthermore, HOLISTIC is collaborating with ICCS on the Data Management Plan (DMP). Lastly, Dr Xexakis mentioned that he might get in touch with specific teams on aspects related to data declaration.</p>		
WP7	<p>Dr Nikas informed the partners that a first version of the project's website will be ready in February, and he requested that the partners check it and provide their feedback. Dr Nikas also informed the partners that the document templates for the project are ready to be used. Lastly, regarding the publications policy from the Commission, Dr Nikas informed the partners that there are no changes in the direction of the Commission. In this context, Dr Nikas reminded the partners of the request regarding open-access journals and institutional agreements.</p>	Finalise the website	HOLISTIC
Project SMEs and European Commission's IP Scan	<p>The last issue discussed was the joint ownership of the open-source models. In this discussion, Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3), Mr Maurizio Garguilo (E4SMA) and Dr Nikas discussed possible policies that can be used, such as the GCAM-World policy. In this context, Dr Xexakis proposed that the smallest burden must be put on model usage (even commercial) and that partners can send licenses to ICCS to examine possible pathways. Furthermore, Dr Nikas and Dr Vielle discussed the fact that the GEMINI model is open source but its database from GTAP is not. Lastly, Dr Nikas suggested that a models' usage should have the lowest number of restrictions possible.</p>	Inform ICCS of potential licenses and matters arising	All modelling partners

3.3 Executive Board Meeting – 22 March 2023

3.3.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 22 March 2023
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Mailing lists (ICCS)
 - MS2: Internal data management (ICCS) – March 2023
 - WP2: Codesing
 - WP2 meetings and progress (update by ETH, ISINNOVA)
 - Engagement strategy & survey (ETH, ISINNOVA, all partners) – April 2023
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - D3.1: Model development strategy (BC3, E4SMA) – March 2023
 - Survey to collect the inputs and outputs (E4SMA)
 - OMNIA physical meeting (03/03, Turin) – aftermath
 - CLEWs physical meeting (24-25/04, Athens) – plan
 - GCAM physical meeting (18/05, Bilbao) – plan
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Consumer side (UM, CESAR, UNIBAS, IAM teams)
 - openTEPES (COMILLAS, IAM teams)
 - Next meetings (Imperial)
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - WP6: Open
 - Open data management plan (ICCS, HOLISTIC) – March 2023
 - Licenses for the six new IAMs (to include in CA final version)
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - D7.1: Visual Identity & website (HOLISTIC) – March 2023
 - Document templates (ICCS & HOLISTIC)
2. Pending requests – ICCS & All Partners
3. Consortium Agreement and partners' requests (ICCS)
4. Any other business

3.3.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS

2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Natasha Frilingou	ICCS
5	Themistoklis Koutsellis	ICCS
6	Panagiotis Fragkos	ICCS
7	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS
8	Jon Sampedro	BC3
9	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
10	Claudia Rodes	BC3
11	Kurt Kratena	CESAR
12	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
13	Elpida Giouleka	CYI
14	Gabriele Cassetti	E4SMA
15	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
16	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
17	Georgia Polutanou	HOLISTIC
18	Andrés Ramos Galán	COMILLAS
19	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
20	Carlo Sessa	ISINNOVA
21	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
22	Mark Sanders	UM
23	Marie Pied	ESMIA
24	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
25	Marc Vielle	EPFL
26	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
27	Rui Mata	UNIBAS
28	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
29	James Price	UCL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	<p>The meeting started with Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) greeting the partners. Afterwards, the discussion moved to the joint ownership issue, for which Dr Nikas informed the partners that per CA this can be decided later on and Mr Maurizio Gargiulo (E4SMA) confirmed. In this context, Dr Nikas also mentioned that the licenses regarding the open-source nature of the models used are currently gathered.</p> <p>Dr Nikas reiterated the request that all partners continuously update their mailing lists.</p> <p>He also informed the partners that the Internal Data Management report (MS2) will be ready by the end of March and that it has to be uploaded as a Milestone in the EC's platform.</p> <p>Dr Nikas closed the meeting by informing the consortium that the GA meeting in Bilbao, Spain will be a 2-day event and that its 2nd day will mainly focus on GCAM. In this context,</p>	<p>Update mailing lists</p> <p>Prepare MS2</p> <p>Prepare a logistic package for the GA meeting in Bilbao</p>	<p>All partners</p> <p>ICCS, HOLISTIC</p> <p>BC3, ICCS</p>

	he mentioned that partners are encouraged to communicate with ICCS or BC3 regarding Visa issues.		
WP2	<p>Next, Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) informed the partners a first draft of D2.1 has been circulated and that the final draft of D2.1 will be ready by end of March.</p> <p>Moreover, Mr Cassolà and Dr Bianca Vienni-Baptista (ETH) discussed a previous idea on survey among the project's partners which will not move forward and Dr Vienni-Baptista suggested that the survey of Task 2.2 must be rediscussed.</p> <p>Next, Dr Vienni-Baptista mentioned that Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) is meeting (physically or virtually) modelling partners to examine what they expect from the stakeholder engagement process. In this context, Dr Vienni-Baptista also mentioned that ETH partners expect frequent communication with partners during the next months, while the ethics part of WP2 is on track.</p>	<p>Prepare the final draft of D2.1</p> <p>Finalise ethics clearance</p>	<p>ISINNOVA, ETH</p> <p>ETH</p>
WP3	<p>The discussion on WP3 started with Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3) informing the partners that he will contact them regarding updates on the WP3 survey related to D3.1</p> <p>Based on this, Dr Gabriele Casseti (E4SMA) informed the consortium that D3.1 is on track, and in the phase of reviewing. Mr Konstantinos Koasidis (ICCS) replied that the 3 required reviews are on track.</p> <p>In this context, Dr Nikas informed the consortium that the kick-off meetings for OMNIA and GCAM are on track, while for the CLEWs-EU meeting an agenda is already circulated.</p>	<p>Communication with partners for the survey</p> <p>Review and completion of D3.1</p>	<p>BC3, Modelling partners</p> <p>E4SMA, BC3, ICCS</p>
WP4	<p>The next matter discussed was WP4, for which Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) made a short presentation informing the partners on the progress of each Task. Regarding Task 4.1 info on cement and iron & steel industries is collected for all 6 IAMs and a meeting for this issue is arranged in May. Task 4.2 is scheduled to start later on but a meeting for MAGPIE is planned for April or May. Regarding Task 4.3, Dr Mittal informed the partners that a joint meeting for Task 4.3, 4.5 and 4.6 took place in March and that a third one will be hosted in May. She also mentioned that preliminary info on the Stocktake process is being collected in the context of Task 4.4. Lastly, she briefed the partners on the meeting organised on the 7th of March on the openTEPES model and she also mentioned that a 2nd meeting will take place in May.</p>		
WP5	<p>Next, Dr Nikas took the floor and informed the partners that WP5 is not active yet, according to the project's timeline, but related work is already being prepared.</p>		
WP6	<p>Afterwards, Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) informed the partners that D6.1 regarding the Data Management Plan is under review. He also mentioned that a short presentation of how it works (machine-actionable DMP) will take place during the next Executive Board meeting when the DMP will be finalised. In this context, Dr Xexakis and Dr Mittal had a short discussion regarding modelling documentation and they</p>	<p>Review and finalization of D6.1</p>	<p>HOLISTIC, ICCS</p>

	<p>concluded that the process will be almost the same, with minor deviations mainly related to metadata issues.</p> <p>Next, coming back to the licensing aspects, Dr Nikas and Dr Panagiotis Fragkos (ICCS) had a discussion on modelling licenses. They mentioned that the consortium might be able to change things about licenses during the project’s progress, but they also stressed that a final form should be chosen when the GitHub pages will be ready. In this context, Dr Xexakis, replying to Dr Fragkos, mentioned that the project’s aim is not just to upload the models but to make them really open to the public.</p>		
WP7	<p>Regarding WP7, Ms Georgia Polutanou (HOLISTIC) informed the consortium that D7.1 reviews are done (currently under finalisation) and that the followers of the project’s social media accounts are increasing. She also mentioned that there is a video for the website’s dissemination. In this context, Dr Nikas mentioned that the project’s website will be released during the next few days. Ms Polutanou mentioned that the project’s dissemination material (posters, flyers, etc.) are already prepared and available in the project’s website.</p>	Release the project’s website	ICCS, HOLISTIC

3.4 Executive Board Meeting – 28 June 2023

3.4.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting

Wednesday, 28 June 2023

14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - New sister project (!)
 - Participation of DIAMOND partners to the IAMC and ECEMP conferences
 - WP collaboration – Timeline
 - WP2: Codensing
 - Stakeholder Database and milestone (MS2) on stakeholder engagement database
 - WP2-related workshops among ETH & DIAMOND partners
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Update on the modelling survey
 - Overall progress in model development
 - CLEWs: recurring meetings
 - OMNIA: next steps & progress
 - GCAM: GCAM 7.0, GCAM annual meeting
 - Other models (update on timeline)
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Progress on module discussions
 - Workshop on finance, labour, and consumption/wellbeing in Maastricht (Sep 2023)
 - Invitation of Maastricht University to the MORSE Conference (Oct 2023)
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - WP6: Open
 - MS4: Plan on collaboration and synergies (July 2023)
 - I²AM PARIS platform, development pipelines and protocols
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Newsletters
 - Social media
2. Any other business

3.4.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Anastasios Giannousakis	ICCS
5	Russell Horowitz	BC3
6	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
7	Claudia Rodes	BC3
8	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
9	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
10	Gabriele Cassetti	E4SMA
11	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
12	Georgia Polytanou	HOLISTIC
13	Andrés Ramos Galán	COMILLAS
14	Sara Lumbreras Sancho	COMILLAS
15	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
16	Stefano Faberi	ISINNOVA
17	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
18	Paul Zagamé	SEURECO
19	Pierre Le Mouël	SEURECO
20	Marie Pied	ESMIA
21	Marc Vielle	EPFL
22	Stephanie Briers	ETH
23	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
24	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
25	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial
26	James Price	UCL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	The meeting started with Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) greeting the partners and informed the partners that there is a fourth sister project, named CHOICE, in the same area as DIAMOND, Afterwards, he suggested that partners submit abstracts (deadline by the 30 th of June) at the IAMC and ECMP conferences taking place in Venice, Italy in November and virtually in October respectively. He mentioned that BC3, SEURECO and EPFL partners have already expressed their willingness to submit and he proposed that partners that want to submit inform ICCS if their abstracts acknowledge the project. Lastly, Mr Konstantinos Koasidis (ICCS), regarding WP collaborations, mentioned that a couple of workshops will take place in 2023, organized by WP2 but aiming to engage with the other WPs as well, and that this process could feed the 2 nd modelling development cycle.	Submit abstracts to IAMC and ECMP	All partners

WP2	<p>Afterwards, Mr Daniel Cassola (ISINNOVA) informed the consortium that the tools and structure of the stakeholder database is being finalised (MS3). It will contain a tool for its editing and management. He also mentioned that the ISINNOVA team will ask partners to support an initial stakeholder mapping and then receive permissions to include them in the database. Moreover, he stated that the stakeholders should be informed about the project and that this task will collaborate with WP7.</p> <p>Next, Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) mentioned that the scheduled workshops for this period are finished but that there will be 2 or 3 online workshops with modellers from WPs 3 and 4 in the next round of workshops, and that she will get back to the partners with a doodle poll. In this context, she stated that the ETH team is focusing on prioritising model input from stakeholders and that a meeting on that with WP3 and WP4 partners will be arranged. Lastly, Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) and Dr Briers discussed the workshops' themes, with Dr Briers suggesting that the workshops will have a similar structure and that their themes can be determined from a data analysis of the previous workshops, which will be ready in mid-July.</p>	<p>Finalise the tools and structure of the stakeholder database</p> <p>Prepare a milestone report for the database (MS3)</p> <p>Organise modelling workshops in September</p> <p>Arrange a meeting with WP3 and WP4 partners</p>	<p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>ETH, all partners to respond to the doodle poll</p> <p>ETH, All modelling partners</p>
WP3	<p>Next, Dr Gabrielle Cassetti (E4SMA) stated that most issues were already discussed during the General Assembly meeting in Bilbao the previous month and that relevant material uploaded are uploaded in the project's SharePoint. Then, he mentioned that the WP's next step is to understand the current updates on each model as scheduled in November's milestone, and that he will get in touch with modelling teams. Moreover, he mentioned that information regarding linkages with WP4 is necessary and in this direction, bilateral meetings, that will focus on each model, will be arranged. Lastly, all modelling teams quickly briefed the partners on their progress with Dr Nikas proposing that an online follow-up takes place shortly.</p>	<p>Arrange bilateral meetings with modelling teams from WP3 and WP4</p> <p>Online follow-up on model updates</p>	<p>All modelling partners</p> <p>All modelling partners</p>
WP4	<p>Dr Mittal agreed with the idea of the bilateral meetings and mentioned that WP4 is contributing to the WP3 survey to clear issues on linkages. She also mentioned that some discussions can also take place during the physical meeting in the Netherlands in September, where Tasks 4.5 and 4.6 will be discussed. She also proposed that more seminars on models should be organised for better understanding.</p>		
WP5	<p>Next, Dr Jan Ivar Korsbakken (CICERO) mentioned that there are no updates regarding WP5 since it has not started yet, apart from a workshop that took place in June. In this context, Dr Mittal reiterated the potential synergies on exchanging scenarios was organised for the IAM COMPACT project. Lastly, she mentioned that an update on this Task will take place in November</p>		
WP6	<p>Afterwards, Dr Nikas took the floor and mentioned that a 30-50-page plan on synergies (in the form of a milestone) will be</p>	<p>Milestone report on synergies plan</p>	<p>ICCS</p>

	<p>submitted, at the end of July, which will be discussed with sister projects. Dr Nikas has already discussed with Dr Cecilie Mauritzen, who is the coordinator of the WorldTrans project and an SAB member of DIAMOND, about exchanges with this project and a good collaboration is already established. Next, Dr Georgios Xexakis (HOLISTIC) informed the partners that a tool (an Excel file) for vetting scenarios is developed in the I²AM PARIS platform. A video demonstrating the tool will be created and sent to partners via e-mail. He also mentioned that is important to set some openness principles before creating any other tools. In this context, Dr Xexakis and Dr Cassetti agreed that these principles should be discussed with the modelling teams first. Dr Xexakis also suggested that WP6 issues are included in the September workshop and that this workshop should also focus on how WP6 can help WP2. In this context, Dr Briers mentioned that the ETH team will be happy to have a short meeting on this issue.</p>	<p>Submit MS4</p> <p>Prepare a vetting tool for the I²AM PARIS platform</p>	<p>ICCS</p> <p>HOLISTIC</p>
WP7	<p>Next, Ms Georgia Polytanou (HOLISTIC) took the floor and informed the consortium that a 2nd newsletter is sent briefing stakeholders on the project's events and publications and she encouraged partners to inform the HOLISTIC team if any content is missing. Then, she asked that all partners share the newsletter and thanked the consortium for their feedback on the website. Then, Dr Briers suggested that a meeting is arranged to discuss the collaboration of WPs 2 and 7 on translating results.</p>	<p>Share the newsletter</p> <p>Meeting for the collaboration of WPs 2 and 7.</p>	<p>All partners</p> <p>ETH, HOLISTIC</p>

3.5 Executive Board Meeting – 26 July 2023

3.5.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting

Wednesday, 28 June 2023

14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - DIAMOND submissions to the 2023 IAMC and ECEMP conferences
 - EC Request for policy contributions with results at the SME level
 - WP2: Codensing
 - Request to partners to fill in the Stakeholder Database
 - Update on the design of WP2-related workshops among ETH & project partners
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Update on the modelling survey and maintenance strategy
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Coordination call with WPs 2-3 – update
 - Progress on WP4 module/task discussions
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - WP6: Open
 - Update on the submission of the Plan on collaboration and synergies (MS4)
 - I²AM PARIS platform, development pipelines and protocols
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Newsletters
 - Social media
2. Any other business

3.5.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Panagiotis Fragkos	ICCS
5	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS
6	Russell Horowitz	BC3
7	Claudia Rodes	BC3
8	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
9	Gabriele Cassetti	E4SMA
10	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
11	Georgia Polytanou	HOLISTIC
12	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
13	Marie Pied	ESMIA
14	Marc Vielle	EPFL
15	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
16	Stephanie Briers	ETH
17	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
18	Leigh Martindale	Imperial
19	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial
20	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
21	James Price	UCL
22	Michael Obersteiner	Oxford
23	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	The meeting started with Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) greeting the partners and extended an invitation from DG CLIMA to contribute on work related to the impacts on SMEs associated with the climate transition (related to, for example, competitiveness, employment, structural shifts etc.); in case partners can offer any insights, they are kindly invited to do so by end of July. He also updated the partners on the currently known submissions to the IAMC and ECEMP.		
WP2	Afterwards, Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) reiterated the request to contribute to the initial database of stakeholders to engage in our co-creation/co-development activities, asking the partners to send potential stakeholders contacts. He also mentioned that a report outlining the characteristics of the engagement database has been submitted in June (MS3). After finalising the database, ISINNOVA will contact the stakeholders to scope their interest and level of engagement to be able to map them in the project.	Expand the stakeholder database Organise modelling workshops in September	ISINNOVA ETH

	<p>Next, Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH mentioned that the scheduled workshops for this period are finished and an internal report is being prepared and will be shared with everyone. She then mentioned that the next round of workshops will be held in September and facilitated via miro and clarified the scope. These will be arranged through a Doodle poll and last 2-3 hours each.</p> <p>Dr Gabrielle Cassetti (E4SMA) asked when feedback should be expected from stakeholders; Mr Cassolà replied that the engagement cycle could deliver some feedback by May 2024 to with Dr Cassetti replied that the timing is aligned with the development of the models.</p>			
WP3	<p>Next, Dr Gabrielle Cassetti (E4SMA) reminded all modelling partners to continue updating the IAM survey. He then provided a short update on the models' development:</p> <p>NEMESIS: no update yet as development starts in Autumn</p> <p>CLEWS: data collection has started on electricity, vehicle fleet, industry, heating for EU Member States and the technology list for the energy system. Tech list for land & water modules, as well as a reference system diagram are next.</p> <p>GEMINI-E3 EU: New regions and sectors have been defined and the updated GTAP database is expected to be finalised by the end of July.</p> <p>OPEN-PROM: Migration on GitHub has started to make the model fully open, as well as automate data handling and management. Defined new regions & sectors, development of new naming convention and identification of list of technologies to integrated and data sources.</p> <p>GCAM-Europe: GitHub will be used to collaboratively develop the model. The final regional disaggregation should be tested to finally decide, define the grid regions, using inputs from various sources (e.g., ACER) & continue the implementation of multiple consumers in the global version which will be applied in GCAM-Europe</p> <p>OMNIA: New regions (28) have been defined; industry and upstream sectors are in scoping phase to be finalised in September; draft design on the water module; soft-links with: <i>MagPie</i> - under study, <i>ENGAGE</i> - will be discussed during next OMNIA meeting in August, <i>OPEN TEPEs and behavioural change modeule</i> – to be planned in September</p>	Complete survey	IAM	All modelling partners
WP4	<p>Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) mentioned that they have updated the model template and asked the partners to start using the updated version of the Excel file to clear issues on WP3 – WP4 linkages.</p> <p>She then asked whether WP4 models will be included in the WP2 workshops, and if the meetings will be held separately. Dr Briers replied that WP4 will be part of the workshops; separate meetings make more sense.</p> <p>Finally, Dr Mittal mentioned that a workshop on finance, labour and consumption/wellbeing organised by our</p>	Organise seminars on models	more on	All modelling partners
		Organise workshop on finance etc	on	UM

	partners at Maastricht in 21-22 September.		
WP5	- <i>Note:</i> CICERO colleagues were on leave and could not participate in this EB Meeting.	-	-
WP6	Dr Nikas took the floor and mentioned that a 30-50-page plan on synergies (MS4) will be submitted, at the end of July, which will be discussed with sister projects. Afterwards, Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) briefly demonstrated the vetting / validation tool created in I ² AM PARIS (link), explaining that the purpose of the platform is to validate modelling variables (model name, region, variable name, units, etc.), and perform a basic sum check across regions along with a vetting routine. He then asked the partners to provide feedback and suggestions for improvement. Dr Mittal asked whether new vetting rules can be added on the next IPCC cycle (special reports or AR7). Dr Xexakis replied that the tool's code will be open and new rules can be easily added.	MS4 report HOLISTIC to communicate about the vetting tool, partners to check	ICCS HOLISTIC, ICSS, Modelling partners
WP7	Next, Ms Georgia Polytanou (HOLISTIC) informed the consortium that a 3 rd newsletter will be sent next month. She also encouraged partners to contact HOLISTIC in case they need visualisation/content for dissemination purposes.		

3.6 Executive Board Meeting – 20 September 2023

3.6.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 20 September 2023
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Results of DIAMOND submissions to the 2023 IAMC and ECEMP conferences
 - Discussion on the organisation of the next General Assembly
 - WP2: Codensing
 - Request for outstanding partners to fill in the Stakeholder Database.
 - Elaboration on the next steps/timeline for receiving permissions from the stakeholders
 - Update on the organisation of the two WP2-related workshops
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Progress on WP4 module/task discussions
 - Update on the organisation of the “labour, finance, and final demand” workshop in Maastricht
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - WP6: Open
 - Feedback on the validation tool
 - I²AM PARIS platform, development pipelines and protocols
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Newsletters
 - Social media
2. Any other business

3.6.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Natasha Frilingou	ICCS
5	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS
6	Anastasis Giannousakis	ICCS
7	Russell Horowitz	BC3
8	Claudia Rodes	BC3
9	Jon Sampedro	BC3
10	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
11	Gabriele Cassetti	E4SMA
12	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
13	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
14	Andrés Ramos	COMILLAS
15	Sandra Lumbreras	COMILLAS
16	Stefano Faberi	ISINNOVA
17	Paul Zagamè	SEURECO
18	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
19	Mark Sanders	UM
20	Tania Treibich	UM
21	Marie Pied	ESMIA
22	Stephanie Briers	ETH
23	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
24	Victoria Herbig	ETH
25	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
26	Isabella Butnar	UCL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	<p>The meeting commenced with Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) greeting the consortium. Next, Dr Nikas proceeded to WP1 starting by requesting that partners that with submissions to ECEMP to contact him since the consortium aims to chair some sessions.</p> <p>Then, Dr Nikas opened the discussion on the organization of the next General Assemble which will take place between November and January and offered the choices of a physical or a fully online event. Many colleagues suggested that this depends on the scope of the meeting, raised the aspect of reducing flying, if necessary, while some partners (UM, ETH) offered to organise a future GA, but they need an early notice. Dr Nikas mentioned that the first day of the meeting would focus on all WPs and the roadmap of upcoming tasks and deliverables and that the second day would have an SAB</p>	<p>Inform ICCS on ECMP submissions</p> <p>Organise the next General Assembly</p>	<p>All partners</p> <p>ICCS, All partners</p>

	<p>session as well as sessions focusing on specific aspects, and that the ICCS team will reflect on the scope of these dedicated sessions after exchanges with the partners and come back to the issue in the next EB meeting.</p>		
WP2	<p>Mr Stefano Faberi (ISINNOVA) informed the partners that he will send a review from the first database, mentioning some regional and sectoral (i.e., field of origin) unbalanced. Mr Konstantinos Koasidis (ICCS) proposed that the ICCS team can filter the Greek database, but that the ICCS team works on a global one as well. Moreover, he mentioned that an email can be prepared and sent in October to stakeholders to collaborate with them, informing them about the project and including a small survey focusing on their relevance with modelling tools. In this context, Mr Faberi proposed that partners suggest more questions but keep them short. Next, Dr Nikas replied mentioning that having an imbalanced stakeholder pool is somehow expected since the consortium focuses on energy and climate issues.</p> <p>Next, Dr Briers informed the consortium that ETH would host the first online workshops on the 26th of September and the 3rd of October. She also mentioned that they would like to co-create their workshops with the rest of the partners and that they will make a report on the first interaction with the project's partners.</p>	<p>Prepare the communication with the stakeholders</p> <p>Host the first online workshops</p>	<p>ISINNOVA</p> <p>ETH</p>
WP3	<p>Next, Dr Gabriele Casseti (E4SMA) took the floor and provided the latest updates on WP3 and those collected from modelling teams. He also informed the consortium that the preparation of MS5 is in progress. In this context, Dr Nikas replied that a report is expected for MS5 which will be sent to the Project Officer (not uploaded in CORDIS). Afterwards, Dr Mittal proposed that insights from the survey on the linkages between WP3 and WP4 can be added to MS5, with Dr Casseti replying that all WP3 teams will have bilateral calls with WP4 teams.</p>	<p>Prepare MS5</p>	<p>E4SMA, BC3 All modelling teams</p>
WP4	<p>Regarding WP4, Prof Tania Treibich (UM) briefed the partners on the upcoming 2-day workshop that would take place in Maastricht, mentioning that on the first day, the UM team's view and suggestions on the IAM models would be discussed whereas on the second day, the views of IAM modellers would be the main focal point. Lastly, Dr Mittal mentioned that WP4 modellers can communicate with WP3 teams during the workshop.</p>	<p>Host the Maastricht workshop</p>	<p>UM</p>
WP5	<p>Dr Jan Ivar Korsbakken (CICERO) informed the consortium that there are no updates regarding WP5.</p>		
WP6	<p>Next, Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) mentioned that his team is working on the validation tool and asked partners to inform them if there are any issues. Moreover, he mentioned that IPCC Working Group 3 has shown interest in a collaboration among modellers.</p>	<p>Further develop the validation platform</p>	<p>HOLISTIC, ICCS</p>

WP7	Then, Mr Koasidis informed the partners the Social Media posts are going well, and the project's website was being frequently updated with new content.		
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3.7 Executive Board Meeting – 25 October 2023

3.7.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 25 October 2023
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Decisions on the organisation of the next General Assembly
 - Update on D1.2 Report on project and SAB Meetings
 - Sister project WorldTrans Annual Meeting & SAB event invitation (March 2024)
 - WP2: Codesing
 - Aftermath of the WP2 workshops: Follow-up meeting
 - Next steps of stakeholder engagement (including update on database)
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Progress on “MS5: Planned model updates & expansions”
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Progress on WP4 module/task discussions
 - Aftermath of UM workshop WP5: Apply & Explore
 - WP6: Open
 - Progress on the validation tool, and development of visualisation tool
 - I²AM PARIS platform, development pipelines, and protocols
 - Community building
 - IAMC 2023 – who’s joining?
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Newsletters
 - Social media
2. Any other business

3.7.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
4	Natasha Frilingou	ICCS
5	Russell Horowitz	BC3
6	Claudia Rodes	BC3
7	Jon Sampedro	BC3
8	Dirk-Jan Van de Ven	BC3
9	Gabriele Cassetti	E4SMA
10	Sonja Sechi	E4SMA
11	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
12	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
13	Andrés Ramos	COMILLAS
14	Sandra Lumbreras	COMILLAS
15	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
16	Stefano Faberi	ISINNOVA
17	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
18	Kurt Kratena	CESAR
19	Paul Zagamè	SEURECO
20	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
21	Mark Sanders	UM
22	Tania Treibich	UM
23	Marie Pied	ESMIA
24	Stephanie Briers	ETH
25	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
26	Victoria Herbig	ETH
27	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
28	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
29	Vignesh Sridharan	Imperial
30	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
31	Marc Vielle	EPFL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	<p>The meeting commenced with Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) greeting the consortium. Dr Nikas informed the consortium regarding an upcoming personnel change in ICCS, as Prof. Haris Doukas (ICCS) has been elected mayor of Athens, starting officially on January 1st, 2024, and that he will have to step out of his duties as Professor. ICCS will ensure that the partners face no disruptions.</p> <p>Next, Dr Nikas commented on D1.2 Report on project and SAB Meetings, due in November, which is on track. Based on the discussion in the previous EB, Dr Nikas proposed that the</p>	<p>Doodle poll for the next GA</p> <p>Preference for the next General Assembly</p> <p>Inform ICCS on physical participation in</p>	<p>ICCS</p> <p>All partners</p> <p>All partners</p>

	<p>next General Assembly be an online meeting since one physical meeting has already taken place in 2023 and that a doodle poll would be sent to all partners ASAP. Partners could offer to host the next physical GA, which will take place in the summer of 2024.</p> <p>Dr Nikas also mentioned that he was invited to invited Dr Nikas to participate in the WorldTrans annual meeting & SAB event, which will take place in March 2024 in Bergen, Norway and asked whether any partners (especially our Norway-based partner CICERO) might be interested in joining and representing IAM COMPACT in case he could not join physically.</p> <p>Dr Nikas asked whether any partners are planning to join COP28 physically, as part of their institute's activities, of another project, or for personal interest since there is an opportunity to host a side-event at the Greek Pavillion; Dr Alaa Al Khourdajie (Imperial) has expressed interest in joining COP28, possibly presenting a study which revolves around CCS with focus on COPs and international climate negotiations; and Dr Steve Pye (UCL) might also be joining.</p>	COP28.	
WP2	<p>Dr Stephanie Briers (ETH) thanked the consortium for their participation in the workshops; in total 23 participants joined. ETH is preparing a workshop report which is focused on better organising stakeholder activities, and what DIAMOND partners expect from stakeholders to be sent out next week and are kindly asking all partners to provide feedback.</p> <p>Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) reminded the partners to send their contributions to the stakeholder database. The database currently consists of 300 stakeholders, but there is currently an imbalance in terms of representations (a lot of climate & energy experts, very few people from other disciplines such as health, and SSH). An initial survey is been prepared to be sent to potential stakeholders asking for their permission and scoping their interest to engage with DIAMOND, after feedback received.</p>	<p>Prepare and share workshop report</p> <p>Send stakeholders' contacts to ISINNOVA</p>	<p>ETH</p> <p>All partners</p>
WP3	<p>Next, Dr Dirk-Jan Van de Ven (BC3) gave a very brief outlook of WP3, giving the floor to Dr Gabriele Cassetti (E4SMA) to elaborate on the preparation of MS5 which is due in November. Together with ICCS, they have discussed the shape of the milestone, which will be a report where modelling teams will contribute a 5-pager, in case of a single model, or a 10-pager for multi-team models. The contributions should be finalised by November 13th & E4SMA will provide a template (based on the OMNIA model) with the preferred structure and necessary information the next week. Regarding participation in Maastricht's workshop, CYI (CLEWs) & EPFL (GEMINI) teams participated physically, while all other modelling teams expect BC3 to participate online.</p> <p>Regarding model updates:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEMESIS: reviewed the multi-regional I/O database & 	Prepare MS5	E4SMA, All modelling teams

	<p>started mapping the geographical scope of the model, the economic activity & the time coverage. Collecting & processing data on the source of revenue of households both by income & by consumption. They started coding the implementation of household split by income deciles using python</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLEWs: technology commodity list finalised; collection of data on energy, land & water is ongoing; GitHub repository has been set up; the reference system diagram is going to be developed for the entire model in the coming weeks. • GEMINI: mapped GHG emissions from GitHub database to IPCC classifications: if possible also share with other teams; started upgrading biofuel database in line with GTAB database • OPEN-PROM: incorporated more data, developed model results validation tools against historical & reference data • OMNIA: advanced the design of the industry sector, including ammonia, aluminium & ferrous metals; a draft of the upstream sector design is ready; The team has started designing the soft linking with ENGAGE CGE (Task 4.1); made initial calls with UNIBAS on integrating behavioural change aspects (Task 4.6) & openTEPES (Task 4.7) • GCAM: in the process of disentangling all European regions within the global model. This step required a lot of debugging; the next step will be to change the data system to include Europe-specific data. 		
<p>WP4</p>	<p>Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) highlighted the outcomes from the Maastricht workshop. First, a literature review is ongoing looking at how finance, labour and consumer behaviour are represented in different models and also what kind of models exist in the literature, as well as what is included in the literature so far, and what kind of improvements are required. Second, they had an initial discussion on how these aspects can be integrated into DIAMOND’s models, with its outcome to be included in MS5. She also informed the partners that meeting notes from the workshop have been uploaded on the project’s SharePoint.</p> <p>Regarding WP4 tasks, each core modelling team should discuss with sectoral modelling teams how they are planning to link the models. OMNIA team has already met with UCL regarding the linkages with the ENGAGE-CGE to decide on how the models will be linked; the same with MagPIE (Task 4.2). Dr Mittal asked all modelling teams for an update regarding all tasks within WP4 in order to have the linkages properly mapped out in time for MS6.</p>	<p>Discuss how sectoral model linkages can be implemented</p> <p>Linkages mapped out properly before MS5</p>	<p>All modelling partners</p> <p>All modelling partners</p>
<p>WP5</p>	<p>CICERO colleagues were not present in the call, yet WP5 will soon start preparing for its first WP5 tasks (soon to kick-off:</p>		

	Task 5.1).		
WP6	<p>Next, Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) mentioned the upcoming update of I²AM PARIS platform (users, uploads, speed). His team has been working on a faster and more interactive visualisation method for the platform, which will be released soon, and shared with everyone for feedback. In terms of community building, he mentioned a meeting that DIAMOND participated in last month regarding a new platform (Climate Research Network) seeking to connect & gather inputs from climate modelling teams, especially in the contest of WGI & WGII.</p> <p>Dr Mittal mentioned that during a meeting with UK policymakers, there was a lot of criticism regarding the scenarios selected for India & other regions, and the fact that only a few teams are handling the selection process. This could prompt a change in scenario selection criteria (validity/feasibility checks) coming from the IPCC.</p> <p>Finally, Dr Nikas briefed the consortium regarding DIAMOND’s participation in the ECEMP, chairing one session and presenting three papers acknowledging the project.</p>		
WP7	Dr Xexakis informed the partners on DIAMOND’s CDE plans, focusing on our participation in the IAMC 2023 conference, which will take place in Venice, November 14-16, 2023.		

3.8 Executive Board Meeting – 22 November 2023

3.8.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Wednesday, 25 October 2023
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Manage & Coordinate
 - Decisions on the organisation of the next General Assembly
 - Participation at the 16th IAMC 2023
 - Update on D1.2 Report on project and SAB Meetings
 - Consortium Agreement finalised
 - WP2: Codensing
 - Elaborations on the results of the workshops and the follow up surveys. Timeline and scope of D2.4 “Stakeholder-informed research questions”
 - Updated on the survey to receive confirmation from the mapped stakeholders.
 - WP3: Update & Upgrade
 - Progress on “MS5: Planned model updates & expansions”
 - Overall progress in model development and short updates for all six core models:
 - OMNIA
 - CLEWs-EU
 - GCAM-Europe
 - NEMESIS-World
 - OPEN-PROM
 - GEMINI-E3 EU
 - WP4: Integrate & Expand
 - Progress on WP4 module/task discussions
 - EGU 2024 announcement (and participation)
 - WP5: Apply & Explore
 - WP6: Open
 - Progress on the validation tool, and development of visualisation tool
 - I²AM PARIS platform, development pipelines, and protocols
 - WP7: Communicate, Disseminate, & Exploit
 - Newsletters
 - Social media
2. Any other business

3.8.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	ICCS
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	ICCS
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	ICCS
4	Eleftheria Zisarou	ICCS
5	Anastasis Gianoussakis	ICCS
6	Russell Horowitz	BC3
7	Claudia Rodes	BC3
8	Jon Sampedro	BC3
9	Dirk-Jan Van de Ven	BC3
10	Benjamin Sanderson	CICERO
11	Gabriele Cassetti	E4SMA
12	Sonja Sechi	E4SMA
13	Maurizio Gargiulo	E4SMA
14	Alessandro Chiodi	E4SMA
15	George Xexakis	HOLISTIC
16	Sandra Lumbreras	COMILLAS
17	Constantinos Taliotis	CYI
18	Daniel Cassolà	ISINNOVA
19	Kurt Kratena	CESAR
20	Paul Zagamè	SEURECO
21	Baptiste Boitier	SEURECO
22	Mark Sanders	UM
23	Tania Treibich	UM
24	Marie Pied	ESMIA
25	Bianca Vienni-Baptista	ETH
26	Victoria Herbig	ETH
27	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
28	Sigit Perdana	EPFL
29	Marc Vielle	EPFL

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	The meeting started with Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) greeting all the partners. Then, he informed them that the next General Assembly Meeting will take place virtually on the 8 th and 9 th of January 2024. He noted that apart from dedicated WP slots, more time will be given to WP2 on Day II since the next six months will require more stakeholder engagement activities. Moreover, he mentioned that a Doodle pool has been sent to the SAB members so they can indicate which one-hour slot most suits them for the SAB session. Afterwards, Dr Nikas proceeded to discuss matters about the project's participation in conferences, commencing by	Organise the next GA meeting	ICCS
		Submit to EGU 2024	All partners
		Finalise D1.2	ICCS

	<p>expressing his gladness that many team members from the consortium attended the IAMC conference in Venice the week before, although the project is still quite new. Additionally, he informed the consortium that DIAMOND partners will be hosting a session at the EGU 2024 conference in Vienna in April 2024, encouraging partners to submit papers by the following January.</p> <p>Next, Dr Nikas informed the consortium that D1.2 regarding the reporting of project meetings is almost finalised, missing only the minutes of the 8th Executive Board Meeting.</p>		
<p>WP2</p>	<p>Next, Dr Vienni-Baptista took the floor and briefed the partners about the report regarding the 2nd phase of the stakeholder engagement workshops, which has been finalised. Afterwards, she encouraged all project partners to fill in the WP2 survey, with Dr Nikas adding that it requires 10-15 minutes and that it is easy to fill in.</p> <p>Following that, Dr Vienni-Baptista also informed the partners about Ms Victoria Herbig’s (ETH) master’s thesis about stakeholder inclusivity which will have DIAMOND as a case study providing useful findings for the project. In this context, she also informed the consortium that Ms Herbig will contact them for some related interviews and that a survey will be rolled-out shortly.</p> <p>Then, Mr Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA) took the floor, thanking ICCS, ETH and HOLISTIC partners for their feedback on the stakeholder invitation letter.</p> <p>Next, he proceeded to the issues regarding the stakeholder database, which now includes 276 stakeholders. The main issue is the lack of stakeholders from various scientific fields such as social and humanitarian sciences, labour, agriculture etc. He also mentioned that the database will be constantly enhanced with more stakeholders; hence this issue might be resolved. In this context, Dr Nikas proposed that the stakeholders under the “climate” affiliation (almost 50% of the whole database) can be disaggregated into other categories regarding other fields of expertise, since “climate” can be considered an “umbrella” for a wide variety of fields. Moreover, Dr Nikas mentioned that ETH has contacts from the social and humanitarian sciences as well as from the health sector. In addition, he also proposed that UM partners find stakeholders with expertise in labour issues and Prof Mark Sanders (UM) agreed. In this context, Mr Konstantinos Koasidis (ICCS) proposed that stakeholders, when contacted, can assess their field differently, solving the initial issue, adding that if the problem persists, mitigation options are available such as contacting colleagues from the IAMC stakeholders’ session. Next, Dr George Xexakis (HOLISTIC) mentioned that there might the mapping of stakeholders could be revisited for experts in social and humanitarian sciences that are classified otherwise, with Mr Cassolà</p>	<p>Fill in the WP2 survey</p> <p>Enhance the stakeholder database</p>	<p>All partners</p> <p>ETH, ISINNOVA, All partners</p>

	proposing to check this issue. Lastly, Dr Vienni-Baptista and Mr Cassolà discussed the self-assessment of stakeholders and requested that all partners send some stakeholder information.			
WP3	<p>Regarding WP3, Dr Gabriele Casseti took the floor, stating that the report for MS5 is being finalised, mentioning that it misses only the update plan of OPEN-PROM. In this context, Dr Anastasis Giannousakis (ICCS) replied that his team would deliver the required text in the following days. In this context, Ms Sonja Sechi (E4SMA) informed the partners that E4SMA would need only a couple of days to merge all model update plans into the final report, with Dr Casseti stating that they will upload a draft version by Friday, asking partners to review it by Monday. Then, Dr Nikas Mr Koasidis agreed with this timeline since there would be sufficient time to copyedit the final version.</p> <p>Lastly, Dr Casseti and Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven briefed the consortium on the latest progress of the project's IAMs, focusing on few matters that are not included in the MS5 report.</p>	Finalise report	MS5	E4SMA, ICCS
WP4	Prof Adam Hawkes (Imperial) mentioned that WP4 teams are focusing on WP3 tasks and that there is no further update on WP4. In this context, Dr Nikas informed the consortium that Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) joined an IAMC diagnostics group, from which she can draw useful insights for the project.			
WP5	Next, Dr Ben Sanderson (CICERO) briefed the partners on the progress of climate tools and mentioned that his team will contact Dr Mittal to further discuss how they will proceed. He also mentioned that WP5 kicks off in the following January; hence they have done only preparatory work so far.			
WP6	Regarding WP6, Dr Xexakis mentioned that the server hosting tools for DIAMOND needs to be updated and that HOLISTIC is already improving some of its tools. He also encouraged partners to contact him if they deem that some tools must be updated first. Lastly, on WP6, he suggested that the consortium should discuss with the PRISMA and ENGAGE project teams to avoid creating the same tools.	Update the server		HOLISTIC
WP7	Next, he mentioned that DIAMOND had an important presence at the IAMC conference, with Mr Koasidis informing the consortium of the number of papers and posters presented. Lastly, Dr Nikas mentioned that a communications campaign will be prepared for the COP28 side event, an event that will feature Prof Doukas, Prof Steve Pye (UCL), Dr Alaa Al Khourdajie (Imperial) and Prof Ryna Cui (UMD).	Prepare a communications campaign for the COP-28 side event		HOLISTIC, ICCS

4 Scientific Advisory Board meetings

The Scientific Advisory Board consists of external to the project, highly esteemed individuals, tasked to provide technical and scientific guidance to the project. The selection and appointment of SAB members is the responsibility of the General Assembly (GA), which is composed of one representative from each beneficiary and the Project Coordinator. The Terms of Reference, originally proposed synthesis, and formulation of the SAB have been documented in the first milestone (MS1) report. The Project Coordinator—in cooperation with all partners—has contacted various stakeholders such as academics and climate change mitigation experts and invited them to be part of DIAMOND’s SAB, which currently consists of 8 members, ensuring a variety of practical/scientific expertise and gender balance. The synthesis can be modified if new opportunities/challenges arise.

4.1 1st SAB Session: 17 May 2023

4.1.1 Minutes

The SAB session was scheduled during the 1st General Assembly (GA) meeting of the project, which took place in Bilbao, Spain on the 16th and 17th of May 2023, in hybrid format, thereby allowing partners to join online as well. In particular, the SAB members joined virtually, via Microsoft Teams, either due to professional obligations, strict schedules, or travel limitations. With the synthesis of the SAB not yet finalised at the time of the GA, participating members included Dr Cecilie Mauritzen, Dr David McCollim, Prof Hannah Daly, and Prof Brian O’ Gallachoir, who were able to attend the SAB session, as well as some parts of the rest of the GA meeting. Specifically, the SAB session took place on the 2nd day of the GA meeting, after the four WP4-specific workshops were concluded. In this way, SAB members had the opportunity to join online from Day 1, to get informed on the project’s progress as well as to gain some insights into the specific work proposed to be done regarding the interlinkages of the project’s IAMs (that are expected to be enhanced and upgraded) with various sectoral modules.

Since this was the first formal interaction (aside from e-mail exchanges) with the SAB, the session started with Dr Alexandros Nikas (ICCS) introducing the SAB members to the project, presenting the project’s duration, scope, and partners comprising the consortium. He also showcased the project’s objectives as stated in the project’s Grant Agreement. In this context, he provided a schematic overview of the project’s methodology and structure, focusing on the IAM enhancements that the project aims to achieve (WP3) as well as their interlinkages with sectoral modules (WP4). Then, Dr Nikas briefed the SAB on the Horizon Europe ecosystem that DIAMOND is part of. This ecosystem is split into three categories: a) projects focusing on enhanced integrated assessments towards global goals using IAMs, b) projects aiming at the improvement of the modelling capacity in IAMs (with DIAMOND being one) and c) projects aiming to better understand the interactions between mitigation and adaptation. Next, he demonstrated the Pert diagram of the project, illustrating the interactions between WPs, and a schematic representation of the stakeholder engagement process. His presentation also included the progress so far, regarding the IAMs’ developments and, in the same context, he proceeded by presenting the enhancements that are envisioned to take place by the end of the project. Moreover, he briefed the SAB members on the project’s endeavours to follow the FAIR principles, stressing the machine-actionable Data Management Plan (the use of Argos was also mentioned) and the project’s GitHub repository. Finally, before giving the floor to the members of the SAB, Dr Nikas presented the SAB synthesis at the time (i.e., those members that had already confirmed their participation, as well as those pending).

The first SAB member to take the floor was Dr Cecilie Mauritzen who congratulated the consortium on the progress and introduced herself. She is an oceanographer at the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (MET Norway) and has participated in WGI of the latest IPCC’s Assessment Report. She has obtained her PhD from MIT and was a

former director of CICERO (a DIAMOND partner), with her main expertise deriving from her research work in MET Norway. She is currently the project coordinator of WorldTrans, one of DIAMOND's sister projects. Next, Prof Hannah Daly took the floor and mentioned that she was happy to see familiar faces among the consortium, before also introducing herself. She is a Professor at University College of Cork (UCC), with a PhD from UCL. Her postdoc research has focused on TIMES and IAMs in general. She has participated in many EU research projects, but she has also worked with IEA, among others on the World Energy Outlook. In the last 4 years, she has been in UCC examining energy system pathways for Ireland. She mentioned that Ireland is an interesting case since the country has an important agricultural sector, an issue that she and her team have investigated extensively. Lastly, she noted that her previous research had focused on heterogeneity and behavioural change and that she would like to exchange experience and ideas in that particular domain—a core area of research in DIAMOND. Next in line was Prof Brian O' Gallachoir, who greeted the consortium, mentioning that the project seems very ambitious and expressing his happiness to be invited to join the SAB. Then, he introduced himself. Like Prof Daly, he is a professor at University College of Cork; he is a modelling expert that has worked with the Irish TIMES, LEAP, and PLEXOS models. He also participates in the IEA's technology collaboration programme (ETSAP), serving as Chair of the Executive Committee. During the past year, he had participated in the development of a new global TIMES model (TIMES-Geo), which will be open-access, a critical expertise that shall prove handy in terms of the OMNIA model development. During the past ten years, he has studied the societal aspects of energy transitions and climate action on how to support citizens and communities as well as on how to engage with citizens, with a focus on rural areas of Ireland—a challenging field due to the lack of qualitative and quantitative data. He finally mentioned that he is happy to be part of the SAB and offer his expertise as the work progresses. Last but not least, Dr McCollum seconded some of Prof O' Gallachoir's points and mentioned that he is happy to be in the SAB on such an ambitious project. He introduced himself, starting with his research capacity at the Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL; located in Southeastern USA). Prior to joining ORNL, he had worked at the Electric Power Research Institute (EPRI) and IIASA. He has worked with various IAMs, including MESSAGE, TIMES, and GCAM as well as economic models, focusing on a state-level analysis. During the last 5-10 years, he has worked on issues such as investments and finance, demand-side responses, consumer behaviour, and sustainable finance. He also mentioned his experience in WGIII of the latest IPCC's Assessment Reports as well as in communities of practice, focusing on the US and Research-to-Operations-to-Research actions. In conclusion, he expressed his gratitude for having the opportunity to participate in the SAB.

After the SAB members introduced themselves, Dr Nikas took the floor to propose some initial ideas on how the cooperation between the consortium and the SAB can take place. First, he expressed his happiness to get to know the SAB members. Then, he stated that, in acknowledgement to their busy schedule, the SAB members have no specific obligation towards the project, but their valuable feedback and insightful advice would be much appreciated whenever meaningful and convenient. Dr Nikas suggested that the consortium keep the SAB updated on the progress of the project via regular e-mails (e.g., bimonthly exchanges). He also mentioned that the consortium aims to organise SAB meetings as well as try to meet the SAB members physically if the opportunity presents itself. Moreover, he stated that the consortium would like to receive feedback from the SAB on dedicated aspects and proposed that the consortium can get in touch with specific members of the SAB focusing on issues around their (e.g., Prof O' Gallachoir can be an excellent asset for the development of the OMNIA model, drawing on his experience with TIMES and his role in IEA-ETSAP, much like Dr. McCollum on GCAM). Lastly, Dr Nikas proposed ways to facilitate things regarding the communication between the SAB and the project's partners.

Dr Nikas then asked for the SAB's feedback and some preliminary ideas. Dr Mauritzen took the floor and stressed the importance of stakeholder engagement since it is hard to find citizens interested in such activities. She expressed her personal interest in collaborating in this endeavour, with WorldTrans sharing similar aspirations, and she also suggested that she meet some of the partners physically at the IAMC meeting in Venice. Lastly, she

mentioned that receiving information feels a little passive and she encouraged an active dialogue between the SAB members and the consortium. In response, Dr Nikas said that the consortium tries to actively engage with citizens and that it plans to submit a plan for synergies and collaborations with other projects, which will be shared with the SAB members for feedback. He also mentioned that the consortium always aspires to be represented in IAMC meetings and that colleagues will be in touch with the SAB for a plan regarding synergies. Dr McCollum agreed with Dr Mauritzen and expressed his willingness to provide advice if needed. He stressed the importance of opening doors on matters that the consortium may not be as aware of, such as conferences. In this context, Dr Nikas replied that the consortium really likes this notion of the SAB and genuinely endeavours to make it work, and he agreed with the points raised by the SAB members. Next, Prof O' Gallachoir invited consortium partners to participate in ETSAP's biannual meetings with Dr Nikas replying that the consortium is already discussing this idea and that it will communicate with Prof O' Gallachoir on further details. In this discussion, Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) expressed that Dr McCollum's experience with scenarios can be very insightful and she asked him if he is aware of any relevant conferences. In this context, Dr McCollum informed Dr Mittal that an IPCC report on scenario development will be published in July, providing useful insights for the project's progress on scenarios.

After the SAB members made their comments, Dr Mauritzen took the floor and offered a brief presentation of the WorldTrans project. The project belongs in the same scientific area as DIAMOND, aiming to improve state-of-the-art IAMs and tackle their weaknesses, and aims to produce transparent assessments for new communities (experts and citizens alike). Specifically, the weaknesses targeted by the WorldTrans project are the limited climate feedback considered in IAMs, their limited representation of heterogeneity, as well as their lack of transparency and stakeholder involvement. The starting point of the project is how to produce consistent outcomes across all three Working Groups of the IPCC's Assessment Reports. Then, Dr Mauritzen presented a graph examining the resolution of models and the number of interlinkages and components. Next, she presented the project's team, including researchers from IIASA, MET Norway, UK MET Office, PIK Potsdam, and Stockholm Resilience Centre among others. The project uses system dynamics based on the simulation tool, "EN-ROADS". Moreover, Dr Mauritzen presented the project's WPs and how each WP revolves around each of the 3 weaknesses to be tackled. In this context, she also demonstrated FRIDA, the model to be developed in the project, and she focused on some preliminary results provided by FRIDA v0.1, examining a baseline scenario. She also mentioned that, during the project, 4 versions of FRIDA will be developed with the first two (v0.1 and v1) expected within 2023. Versions 2 and 3 will be developed and deployed in 2024 and 2025, respectively. Finally, she presented the reasons that the project's consortium is unique in comparison with other consortia focusing on three facts: a) the consortium consists of authors from all three Working Groups of the IPCC's Assessment Report, b) the project uses 'the best System Dynamics engine' available, and c) it also includes a great team regarding social aspects examined in the project. At this point, she concluded her presentation and Dr Nikas thanked the SAB members for attending this session. He mentioned that their comments and notes were very insightful.

4.2 Meeting with SAB members at the IAMC 2023 meeting: November 2023

Several members of the DIAMOND project, including colleagues from ICCS, BC3, Imperial, HOLISTIC, UMD, EPFL, and UCL, had the opportunity to briefly meet with two members of the SAB (Dr. David McCollum and Dr. Cecilie Mauritzen) at the Sixteenth Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC) in Venice, Italy (November 14-16, 2023), exchanging experiences from the conference and ideas on next steps. Both members shared they were happy with the six research presentations acknowledging the DIAMOND project.